

Common data pool on sustainability standards and competitiveness

MATS Deliverable 3.4

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Summary

In D3.4 a common data pool on sustainability standards and competitiveness has been created. The focus countries are Germany, France, Italy, USA, Brazil, Argentina and South Africa. Moreover, for dairy, Zimbabwe and Algeria have been investigated. For beef, Morocco and Namibia are also covered.

Competitiveness has been studied with the internationally recognized approach of “typical farm”, using a model farm representing the most common farm type for a specific product in a specific country or region. Details about the method are described as well as the characteristics of the typical farms (size, annual production, number of labour units, hectares cultivated). Following this approach, production costs (labour costs - in terms of family labour and paid labour -, wages, prices), subsidies and cattle returns are reported.

Moreover, the focus is on imports and exports: the top five import-export destinations (for dairy and beef products) have been analysed in term of quantities for the main commodities. Additionally, an in-depth cross-country analysis on import and export relationships has been addressed: trade between each country and all the others has been described. Trade tariffs have been expressed (when available) as percentage in the trade flows for the main products and classified according to duty type (effectively applied tariffs, bound tariffs, most favoured nations tariffs, etc.).

Social sustainability has been investigated with reference to some SDGs strictly linked with the case studies on which this deliverable is based on. In particular, the social aspect is a primary focus in Case Study (CS) 10 and 13, which fall within the action area of SDGs no. 1, 2, 3, 6. Given the complexity of the topic, SDGs have been translated to the more operational disclosures of the GRI Standards -Global Reporting Initiative Standards- which represent global best practice for reporting publicly on a range of economic, environmental and social impacts. A summary table with the translation of the used SDG into the GRI system is also provided as part of a data pool on environmental and social sustainability standards relevant for agricultural trade. In particular, in order to investigate the level of national compliance with labour rights and the consistency between national legislations and the market dynamics, a challenging work on existing legislation on labour

standardization has been carried out, for each engaged country. The result is an excel database, which enables to compare different countries and to understand the dynamics of the trade mechanism through the partner network. The main sections of this database are working time, paid leaves, occupational health and safety, social welfare, payments and trade rights. The sources of this information are the main official government websites and available public databases.

Environmental sustainability has been investigated with the support of Agribenchmark beef (CS10 - beef) and IFCN (CS13 - dairy). As for dairy, single countries have been taken into account and a certain number of typical farms have been studied, in terms of emissions (kg CO₂) per 100 kg of milk produced. As for beef, the approach using typical farms was not feasible, so reference has been done to data provided by literature. In particular, FAO and its publications has been privileged as sources. The limits which have been encountered - and that must be considered in drive conclusions starting from this data - are related to the lack of information as regards to specific countries and to the heterogeneity of data itself, in terms of unit of measurements, approaches and year of investigation.

According to the Grant Agreement Description of Action, T3.4 'Assessment of the environmental and social costs and benefits of FVCs' covered the four case studies (#3, #10, #11, #13). However, a mistake in the GA preparation was to include the case study#3 in T3.4, this is because the data need in T3.4 is at farm level and national level, i.e., typical farm approach, which is not line with the case study#3. Therefore, the implementation of T3.4 does not cover the case study#3. This explanation has been already provided in the first periodic report Section 5.1 'Deviations from Annex 1 and Annex 2 (if applicable)'. In addition, D3.4 does not cover data from the case study #11, as this case study is still undergoing data collection and investigation. Accordingly, D3.4 covers the two case studies #10 and #13.

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Introduction

To support consistency and effective data exchange on sustainability standards and measures of competitiveness across the MATS consortium³, D3.4. contributes with data and standards collection and standardization. In particular, the data pool describes relevant sustainability standards and sources on competitiveness, describes novel data and contributes to standardize them, thereby (i.) enabling a more valid comparison of competitiveness measures across countries and sectors, and (ii.) contributing to more effective data exchange and sharing on sustainability standards across MATS, and (iii.) contributing to the standards and data harmonization debate relevant to policy and research on the nexus of agricultural trade and sustainability.

This common data pool consists of two main parts:

- data pool related *to economic competitiveness*,
- data pool related *to sustainability standards* (environmental sustainability and labour conditions)

Addressing competitiveness and thereby economic sustainability, and social sustainability provides a more comprehensive study of the concept of sustainability in the agricultural trade context.

The creation of a data pool relevant to all case-study countries is a challenging exercise, starting with data collection, since the data sources available for the different case study countries are not equally accessible, and the subsequent standardisation phase therefore needs to take this diversity into account.

On one hand, *competitiveness* can be addressed thanks to international public databases (FAO, COMTRADE EU Commission sources etc.) and private ones (IFCN, Agribenchmark Beef). On the other hand, it is more difficult to have access to data on sustainability standards (environment and working conditions); these are very specific fields that have sometimes been neglected

³ Across case studies and thus commodities and countries; across work packages; making the common data pool an output that can be used as input in MATS case studies and modelling approaches; D3.4. feeding into the MATS Trade Hub.

by the literature, as far as specific countries are concerned (e.g., some African regions).

Moreover, data related to *environmental sustainability* standards encountered in research papers are frequently presented using diverse units of measurement. This variance leads to compatibility issues and complicates comparative analysis, which has for example been the main driver for developing the EU's Product Environmental Footprint methodology and pilot⁴.

For instance, consider emissions associated with beef, which may be reported as CO₂-eq/kg of live weight, CO₂-eq/kg of meat, or CO₂-eq/kg of protein. As a result, preference has been given to papers, primarily reviews, and literature sources in which authors have made efforts to standardize these measurements. However, even when following this approach, it wasn't always feasible to cover all information for all the target countries. Consequently, in some cases, different data with different units of measurement have been provided for the same subject or region. This inconsistency can sometimes be attributed to differences in the underlying models and investigative methods, further complicating the task of ensuring data quality when attempting to achieve uniformity in expression.

Another issue in some countries is to be able to collect up-dated information, in many cases, when present, data are old and refers to previous decades. This, again, contributes to the difficulty of performing comparisons.

With regard to *work-related sustainability* standards, the collection of legislative material, when available, is organised by national agencies/ data sources according to very different structures. It was therefore necessary to first categorise the available information and then try to make the indicators used in the different case studies more practical.

The need to assess these aspects in detail in a project such as MATS that involves entire value chains has been reinforced by recent changes in European policy even beyond the EU's Farm to Fork strategy, whereby sustainability reporting within large companies requires them since 2017 to disclose risks arising from social and environmental issues and the impact of

⁴ https://green-business.ec.europa.eu/environmental-footprint-methods_en

their activities on people and environment.⁵ Furthermore, the recent deforestation-free supply chain directive provides further evidence for the need to standardize data and sustainability standards in the context of global food value chains.

There are several sustainability assessments approaches available today that allow us to position the study of the sustainability of the labour system within the bigger frame in which trade in agri-food is placed:

- ITC – standards map⁶
- UNFSS - United Forum on Sustainability Standards⁷
- FoSDA – Future of sustainable data alliance⁸
- GRI – Global Reporting Initiative⁹

The standardisation is crucial to ensure compatibility and comparability within the pool. The standardization work between the different data sources was building upon previous MATS work "*Addressing the SDG goals through substantiation with the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) indicators*"¹⁰ which suggests a mapping between sub-SDGs and GRI metrics. More details will be provided in the *Social sustainability* section.

The decision to transform the SDG indicators into the disclosure of the GRI mechanism allowed to translate qualitative data into classes that can be compared between the different case studies.

Although the data on working conditions are strictly related to legislation and do not include some real circumstances and exceptions, it was deemed to be an efficient indicator and in line with the requirement of indicator 8.8.2 "*Level of national compliance with labour rights (freedom of association and*

⁵ https://finance.ec.europa.eu/capital-markets-union-and-financial-markets/company-reporting-and-auditing/company-reporting/corporate-sustainability-reporting_en

⁶ <https://standardsmap.org/en/home>

⁷ <https://unfss.org/>

⁸ <https://futureofsustainabledata.com/about/>

⁹ <https://www.globalreporting.org/>

¹⁰ Langeneck L., Steiner B. (2022). *Addressing the SDG goals through substantiation with the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) indicators*, MATS – REPORT 01/2022.

collective bargaining) based on International Labour Organization (ILO) textual sources and national legislation, by sex and migrant status”.

All these challenging elements will be addressed in the elaboration of the case studies in trying to standardize the available information and fill the gaps when data are not available.

Data pool on competitiveness

In this part of the deliverable, different data sets related to competitiveness have been collected. In particular, data related to competitiveness in the dairy and beef sector at farm level (production costs, products prices, labour cost, subsidies) and at international level (import export, trade tariffs). The purpose of D3.4. is to directly provide a valid data pool and data standardization exercise that feeds into cases 10 and 13. Nine case countries are involved in the dairy sector (Italy, Germany, France, Algeria, Zimbabwe, South Africa, Argentina, Brazil, USA) and nine countries in the beef sector (Italy, Germany, France, Namibia, Morocco, South Africa, Argentina, Brazil, USA). To explore farm competitiveness at farm level “the typical farm approach” was used. To explore national competitiveness data, international data sources have been used.

The typical farm approach

A **typical farm**¹¹ is a model farm representing the most common farm type for a specific product in a specific country or region. The necessary technical and economic data to define a typical farm are collected by farmers and local experts. The typical farms are fully comparable as the same standard rules are used. Still, the number of typical farms does not allow statistically significant conclusions. This is a tool used to estimate the total cost of production per unit (i.e., euro/kg of milk, euro/ton wheat etc.).

The approach was developed in various contexts, differentiated by industry:

- the *International Farm Comparison Network* (IFCN), for dairy farms;
- the *Agri-benchmark* networks, for beef and sheep, cereals, fruits and vegetables, and wine;
- the *InterPig network* for pig meat;
- the *International Poultry Production* (IPP) cost analysis performed by the Wageningen University and Research Centre.

Two clusters can be identified in terms of methodological approach: on the one hand, the IFCN and *Agri-benchmark* networks, on the other hand the

¹¹ Source: https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2019-12/ext-study-farmer-costs-fulltext_2014_en_0.pdf

InterPig and IPP networks. In the description of the methodology, the differences will be highlighted.

General structure of the approach

The IFCN and Agri-benchmark networks are composed of country experts, who work in association with focus groups composed of local experts (so-called panel groups), according to a shared methodology. The major objective of these networks is to generate independent, worldwide knowledge on the costs of production and of revenues at farm-level. In order to achieve such knowledge, the central research centres, IFCN Dairy Research Centre, the Thünen Institute, AHDB and WUR-DLO, have developed a reference methodology for the calculation of production costs. The methodology details the steps which need to be taken by the national experts consulted when defining a typical farm.

Selection of regions and locations (*step 1*)

The first stage of the typical farm approach is the selection of the *geographical areas* where the typical farms are located. This step is carried out by the national experts using national statistics. Before establishing a typical farm, the experts have to understand the spatial distribution of the production. The region which produces the largest proportion of the national production should be identified and all main productive regions of the country should be included. The process must be based on a defined reference unit. A number of units, each characterised by peculiar advantages and disadvantages, could serve as indicators - for instance the beef cattle density per 100 ha of agricultural land, the share of dairy farms per km², or the amount of wheat/apple/wine in 1,000 tons per region. The rationale of the indicators is explained here for wheat:

- wheat production per region. This indicator can be misleading if the regions differ substantially in size, causing large regions to appear more relevant than small ones, regardless of wheat density (higher relative importance of wheat production). The same reasoning applies when the regional share of total wheat production is set as an indicator.
- wheat production per ha of arable land. This perspective is closer to agriculture since the indicator excludes non-agricultural land and areas with other crops. However, a region with a very small share of agricultural land and only a few large, wheat-producing farms will be categorized as very important, whereas areas with extensive agricultural land and a higher diversity of products will appear less important.

- wheat production per km². This is a measure for absolute density that considers the different size of the regions, avoiding the disadvantages of the agricultural land perspective. However, it does not measure the relative importance of wheat production compared to other farming systems. This might be misleading when a region is relatively small and surrounded by non-wheat producing areas. Note that a substantial difference exists between productive regions and political regions: the former, in fact, are characterised by natural and bio-climatic conditions, rather than political boundaries.

Definition of the relevant farm population (*step 2*)

Having identified the pertinent regions, it is necessary to establish whether the entire farm population is relevant to the analysis. *Agri-benchmark* and IFCN focus on those farms generating a high share of total income. The rationale is to select farms that are able to generate at least 50% of farmers' income (farms dependent on agricultural income) or to feed at least one person/family. The objective of the analysis must also be considered in the selection process. The selection criteria differ when concentrating on the economic situation of smallholder farms in wheat/beef/dairy production or when tackling international competitiveness.

The next stage concerns the selection of a limited number of farm(s), that differ in terms of production system(s). They should be drawn from the cluster previously selected. For the most important production systems for the typical farm network, it has to be checked if different systems cause differences in the database.

This step in the typical farm approach is best done by the country's experts, on the basis of the available literature and statistical analyses, and/or with the support of local advisors. A stepwise procedure is used, starting with a rather rough classification that will be gradually refined.

Definition of the structure and size of the typical farm (*step 3*)

After defining the relevant types of typical farms and their respective production systems, a decision is taken regarding the size of each typical farm. Their position within the total farm population should be well specified by detailing the number of farms in the population that are larger, smaller, or which fall in the same size category of each typical farm. This task can be accomplished by making use of data about the farm population (which will usually not be available at the level of detail required) or using representative

random samples, which provide key indicators to measure the frequency of certain farm types and sizes (like the Farm Accountancy Data Network of the EU, FADN). A list of the issues that need to be addressed when defining the size of a typical farm and collecting data is provided below. As time and resources are usually limited, it is not always possible to reflect all farm sizes and production systems in a region. Based on the experience of *Agri-benchmark* and IFCN, the following recommendations are offered.

- In a region with minor differences in terms of production systems (for example in the Paris Basin region in France, or in Ireland, for dairy), two farms with the same production system but differing in size should be chosen. One farm should be of moderate size (usually slightly above average), the other farm should be large size and should belong to the approximately 20% of the largest farms of the whole population. Given the typical distribution of farm size classes (various small-sized enterprises with a relatively little share of production, and few large farms with a relatively high share of production, see figure 3.1) this enables the inclusion of a large number of farms and a major share of production in the analysis. Furthermore, it shows size effects: smaller farms could be affected more by specific regulations than large ones, or vice versa.
- Where possible, *Agri-benchmark* and IFCN use regional statistics about farm size distribution to ease the definition of appropriate farm sizes. Obviously, the availability of reliable statistical data is a precondition.
- In a region where (a) size differences are either not pronounced or appear irrelevant and (b) there are significant differences between production systems (e.g., intensive and low-input systems), two farms of about the same size should be chosen, reflecting the different systems.
- The typical farm should have an average management level.
- In order to explore the potentials of a region/country, it is strongly recommended to add one large farm with top management to the set of farms. The technical standards of these top farms provide insight in which technical efficiency level can be reached when the limitations caused by average management are eliminated.

The quality of management is measured in terms of profitability. Farms with an average-level management should show an average level of profit, whereas

top-management farms should rank in the upper 10% of large farms. When profit data are not available, gross margin or the physical productivity per unit of land are used as a proxy.

FIGURE 1 FARM SIZE DISTRIBUTION AND SELECTION OF TYPICAL FARM SIZES

Source: Deblitz and Zimmer, 2005

The question of how many typical farms models are required to represent the production of a specific product of a given country is frequently asked. In quantitative terms, there is no general answer to this question. Two farms are defined as the standard: one average farm and one large farm, both with average management, and eventually a third farm with top management. Beyond this general rule, the number of farms required per country mainly depends on:

- the diversity of production systems including natural conditions, economic conditions, and infrastructure conditions. If production systems are very diverse, an increase in the number of typical farms is required;
- the diversity of farm size structure and its increase usually requires an increase in the number of typical farms;
- the size of the country, since smaller countries usually require less farm types, while larger countries with a great variety of farming systems might be subdivided into different regions;

- the spatial level of analysis, because fewer farms are required for international networks (usually 2 to 4 farms per country. For exceptions see previous point;
- the type of analysis performed. The number of required farms will increase when more adjustments have to be analysed;
- the financial feasibility, i.e., the resources needed to establish and maintain a network of typical farms in a country.

Experience so far has revealed that establishing a national network of typical farms in each country is the most effective method of generating information on a larger number of farms, and by doing so, to get a more detailed picture of both production systems and production costs.

It should however be underlined, that the limited number of typical farms per country does not allow to draw statistically significant conclusions. The results should therefore always be treated with care.

When statistics and resources to define typical farms are not available, a list of minimum criteria applicable to all products covered is made, to guide the first steps in determining a typical farm:

- select the region of the greatest importance for wheat, beef, sheep, dairy, pigs, broilers, apples, wine production in terms of tradable volume produced;
- within the region identified, select the production system with the highest share in regional production of the product to be analysed;
- select the farm size that produces the highest share of the product to be analysed within the production system identified;
- clarify as much as possible the location of the typical farm on the distribution function.

Data collection and assessment criteria (*step 4*)

Data collection is done with the support of local advisors and farmers who know the region, the farms and the production systems. Both *Agri-benchmark* and IFCN use the so-called expert panels, consisting of the responsible scientist, an advisor and from one to six farmers. The panel holds a round table meeting, where all required farm data are collected based on a standard questionnaire, available in several languages. The rationale of the method is a confrontation that creates a consensus on each figure, to properly describe how a typical farm looks like. The most frequent question raised during a panel discussion is: *'can this figure be considered typical for the type of farm we*

want to describe?'. The aim of the analysis distinguishes different intensity levels of farmers' participation, listed and described below:

- a "pre-panel" with only 1 or 2 farmers, appears to be sufficient for *status quo* analysis of economic performance and production costs. Often, it is also possible to base the typical farm data on individual farm data. However, it is necessary (a) to identify and correct the particularities of individual farm data (to transform the latter into typical farm data), and (b) to perform farm visits to 2 to 3 farms with characteristics similar to the typical farm;
- a "full panel" with 4 to 6 farmers is required when farm adjustments to changes in the framework conditions or farm strategies are to be discussed and defined. The main reason is that more management options can be captured with a larger group. For this purpose, the data and the analysis derived from the pre-panel can be used as a basis for discussion.

An essential requirement for the farmers involved is that they must themselves run agricultural enterprises which are similar to the envisaged typical farm.

The collected data are computed by the analytical tools employed in *Agri-benchmark* and IFCN analyses, and results are returned to both the panel and the advisor. This process is repeated until the panel agrees on the results obtained, and a typical farm model is obtained.

In a final step, the results have to be compared with results from other economic analysis, i.e. by comparing the whole-farm profit of the typical farms with representative survey results. Such cross-checking assures that calculations and the typical farm selection procedures are aligned with other scientific results.

The *Agri-benchmark*, IFCN, selected for this study calculate the costs of production and express them in € per weight unit (kg, tons) of product.

Typical farms characteristics

The size of typical farms used for the following analysis are the following:

TABLE 1 DAIRY TYPICAL FARM (N° OF COWS/FARM)

COUNTRY	FARM SIZE							
	DAIRY TYPICAL FARM							
Algeria	6	18	-	-	-	-	-	-
Argentina	180	400	-	-	-	-	-	-
Brazil	34	64	180	120	-	-	-	-
France	100	74	-	-	-	-	-	-
Germany	30	80	154	314	700	1,200	-	-
Italy	154	229	-	-	-	-	-	-
South Africa	650	800	-	-	-	-	-	-
USA	80	500	65	2,350	1200	2600	1100	2272
Zimbabwe	100	425	-	-	-	-	-	-

TABLE 2 BEEF TYPICAL FARM (N° OF COWS/FARM)

COUNTRY	FARM SIZE							
	BEEF TYPICAL FARM							
Argentina	900	380	630	750	1450	26000	-	-
Brazil	35	60	240	300	500	800	1750	5000
France	75	60	200	-	-	-	-	-
Germany	260	280	285	380	525	560	4700	-
Italy	910	2660	-	-	-	-	-	-
Morocco	1	14	36	280	-	-	-	-
Namibia	600	25000	-	-	-	-	-	-
South Africa	3000	75000	-	-	-	-	-	-
USA	8000	75000	-	-	-	-	-	-

The following figures describe the typical farms characteristics in terms of:

- average farm size,
- annual production,
- number of labour units,
- hectares cultivated.

Dairy sector

FIGURE 2 FARM SIZE (N° OF COWS PER FARM)

FIGURE 3 NUMBER OF HECTARES CULTIVATED PER FARM

FIGURE 4 MILK PRODUCTION IN TONS/YEAR (2022)

FIGURE 5 NUMBER OF LABOUR UNITS PER DAIRY FARM

Beef sector

FIGURE 6 FARM SIZE (NUMBER CATTLE SOLD PER FARM PER YEAR)

FIGURE 7 LAND USED IN BEEF FARMS (HA)

FIGURE 8 NUMBER OF LABOUR UNITS PER BEEF FARM

Production costs

In this paragraph, the figures summarise production costs in 2021 in both dairy and beef farms.

FIGURE 9 PRODUCTION TOTAL COSTS IN 2021 IN €/100 KG CW SOLD

FIGURE 10 MILK PRODUCTION TOTAL COSTS IN 2021 IN €/100 KG MILK

Labour costs

In the following section, labour costs in 2021 in both dairy and beef farms have been summarized with several figures.

FIGURE 11 LABOUR COSTS IN BEEF FARMS 2021

FIGURE 12 LABOUR COSTS IN DAIRY FARMS 2021 IN €/100 KG MILK

Wages

The following figures summarise the official wages paid in 2021 on both dairy and beef farms.

FIGURE 13 WAGES PAID IN BEEF FARMS IN €/HOUR

FIGURE 14 WAGES PAID IN DAIRY FARMS IN €/HOUR

FIGURE 15 CALCULATED WAGES FOR FAMILY LABOUR IN BEEF FARMS IN €/HOUR

Prices

In this section, figures summarise the perceived prices in 2021 on dairy and beef farms.

FIGURE 16 BEEF PRICE IN €/100 KG CW SOLD

FIGURE 17 MILK PRICE IN €/100 KG MILK

Subsidies

In this subsection, the figures summarise the subsidies in 2021 on dairy and beef farms.

FIGURE 18 DECOUPLED PAYMENTS IN €/100 KG OF CW SOLD FOR BEEF

FIGURE 19 SUBSIDIES IN €/100 KG MILK PRODUCED

Cattle returns

In this part, the figures summarise the cattle returns in 2021 on dairy and beef farms.

FIGURE 20 CATTLE RETURNS IN DAIRY FARMS IN €/100 KG MILK PRODUCED

Import & export - beef

This chapter reports on the *top import-export destinations* for beef products of the countries investigated in beef sector. Data are expressed in tons.

Argentina

The following tables show the *Argentina's* main export and import partners. Among the project partner countries, Argentina has trade relations with Germany, while it imports beef mainly from Brazil.

TABLE 3 EXPORT - TOP IMPORTERS FROM ARGENTINA (TONS)

BEEF – SUM OF ALL PRODUCT		
	2019	2020
China	427,522	467,867
Russian Federation	65,431	53,365
Chile	30,232	32,994
Israel	24,666	29,084
Germany	25,885	22,060

Source: UNCOMTRADE

TABLE 4 IMPORT - TOP EXPORTERS TO ARGENTINA (TONS)

BEEF – SUM OF ALL PRODUCT		
	2019	2020
Brazil	12,001	8,919
Paraguay	191	648

Source: UNCOMTRADE

Brazil

The following tables show the *Brazil's* main export and import partners. No project partner country imports significant quantities of beef from Brazil, whereas this country buys meat from both the United States of America and Argentina.

TABLE 5 EXPORT - TOP IMPORTERS FROM BRAZIL (TONS)

BEEF – SUM OF ALL PRODUCT		
	2019	2020
China	497,687	868,863
China – Hong Kong	332,170	297,305
Egypt	163,712	122,991
Chile	110,210	89,980
Russian Federation	-	56,963

Source: UNCOMTRADE

TABLE 6 IMPORT - TOP EXPORTERS TO BRAZIL (TONS)

BEEF – SUM OF ALL PRODUCT		
	2019	2020
Paraguay	16,109	25,142
Argentina	14,101	16,612
Uruguay	7,852	5,498
Australia	1,344	1,350
U.S.A.	385	242

Source: UNCOMTRADE

France

The following tables show the *France's* main export and import partners. Italy and Germany import significant quantities of beef. In addition, Germany is among the top five exporters to Brazil

TABLE 7 EXPORT - TOP IMPORTERS FROM FRANCE (TONS)

BEEF – SUM OF ALL PRODUCT		
	2019	2020
Italy	69,059	64,324
Germany	42,464	43,902
Greece	45,659	40,285
Belgium	25,279	26,563
Côte d Ivoire	9,985	9,804

Source: UNCOMTRADE

TABLE 8 IMPORT - TOP EXPORTERS TO FRANCE (TONS)

BEEF – SUM OF ALL PRODUCT		
	2019	2020
Netherlands	76.593	66.136
Ireland	48.614	42.526
Germany	49.137	33.925
Belgium	31.520	30.894
Poland	20.571	19.701

Source: UNCOMTRADE

Germany

The following tables show the *Germany's* main export & import partners. Among the countries importing beef from Germany are Italy and France. The latter also exports to Germany, together with Argentina.

TABLE 9 EXPORT - TOP IMPORTERS FROM GERMANY (TONS)

BEEF – SUM OF ALL PRODUCT		
	2019	2020
Netherlands	89,618	76,680
France	47,642	32,792
Denmark	26,863	26,620
Italy	30,098	25,177
Austria	21,177	22,922

Source: UNCOMTRADE

TABLE 10 IMPORT - TOP EXPORTERS TO GERMANY (TONS)

BEEF – SUM OF ALL PRODUCT		
	2019	2020
Netherlands	112,176	107,779
Poland	55,647	54,809
Austria	44,380	43,704
France	39,920	41,040
Argentina	27,558	23,936

Source: UNCOMTRADE

Italy

Italy has import and export relations of significant quantities of beef with France and Germany.

TABLE 11 EXPORT - TOP IMPORTERS FROM ITALY (TONS)

BEEF – SUM OF ALL PRODUCT		
	2019	2020
Netherlands	19,228	22,223
Germany	17,374	17,113
France	19,675	16,311
Greece	17,654	15,106
Spain	10,586	9,333

Source: UNCOMTRADE

TABLE 12 IMPORT - TOP EXPORTERS TO ITALY (TONS)

BEEF – SUM OF ALL PRODUCT		
	2019	2020
Poland	80,580	69,893
France	64,498	62,555
Netherlands	55,572	58,957
Spain	26,909	29,943
Germany	33,205	26,624

Source: UNCOMTRADE

Morocco

The export and import data are not updated for the year 2020. until the year 2019, Morocco had import relations with Argentina, Brazil and France.

TABLE 13 EXPORT - TOP IMPORTERS FROM MOROCCO (TONS)

BEEF – SUM OF ALL PRODUCT		
	2019	2020
China	13	-
Vietnam	21	-

Source: UNCOMTRADE

TABLE 14 IMPORT - TOP EXPORTERS TO MOROCCO (TONS)

BEEF – SUM OF ALL PRODUCT		
	2019	2020
Argentina	6,007	-
Spain	2,649	-
Brazil	205	-
Poland	123	-
France	94	-

Source: UNCOMTRADE

Namibia

The following tables show the *Namibia's* main export and import partners. Namibia imports and exports significant amounts of beef with the United States of America and South Africa.

TABLE 15 EXPORT - TOP IMPORTERS FROM NAMIBIA (TONS)

BEEF – SUM OF ALL PRODUCT		
	2019	2020
United Kingdom	-	1,609
China	2,614	1,439
Netherlands	2,002	992
South Africa	457	795
U.S.A.	-	527
Andorra	36	-
Norway	1,529	-

TABLE 16 IMPORT - TOP EXPORTERS TO NAMIBIA (TONS)

BEEF – SUM OF ALL PRODUCT		
	2019	2020
U.S.A.	-	327
Australia	149	169
South Africa	552	161
India	14	143
Ireland	-	88
Argentina	38	-
Botswana	41	-

South Africa

The following tables show the *South Africa's* main export and import partners. South Africa does not export significant quantities to the other project partner countries, while it imports beef from the United States of America, Argentina and Namibia.

TABLE 17 EXPORT - TOP IMPORTERS FROM SOUTH AFRICA (TONS)

BEEF – SUM OF ALL PRODUCT		
	2019	2020
China	5,176	12,313
Kuwait	3,051	5,092
Jordan	2,464	4,421
Lesotho	3,187	3,722
Mozambique	3,157	3,189

Source: UNComtrade

TABLE 18 IMPORT - TOP EXPORTERS TO SOUTH AFRICA (TONS)

BEEF – SUM OF ALL PRODUCT		
	2019	2020
U.S.A.	18,599	20,234
Australia	12,589	11,181
United Kingdom	4,006	4,729
Ireland	-	3,996
Argentina	-	3,865
Namibia	8,026	-

Source: UNComtrade

USA

The following tables show the *U.S.A.'s* main export and import partners. No project partner country imports and exports significant quantities of product to rank among the top partners.

TABLE 19 EXPORT - TOP IMPORTERS FROM U.S.A. (TONS)

BEEF – SUM OF ALL PRODUCT		
	2019	2020
Japan	306,325	301,194
Rep. Korea	253,226	244,818
Mexico	191,819	152,665
Canada	76,731	83,754
China	81,720	77,637

Source: UNComtrade

TABLE 20 IMPORT - TOP EXPORTERS TO U.S.A. (TONS)

BEEF – SUM OF ALL PRODUCT		
	2019	2020
Canada	311,322	303,450
Mexico	230,434	257,372
Australia	249,279	228,639
New Zealand	131,652	169,687
Nicaragua	63,366	65,864

Source: UNComtrade

Import & export – dairy

The following tables show the import and export situation by country pairs, for all countries represented by our MATS CS project partners.

The following section provides details of the most relevant import/export relationships. In particular, the trade relations between the countries ranked as the top partners are highlighted. Data are expressed in tons.

Algeria

Algeria is one of the leading consumers of milk in North Africa. Current local fluid milk production is estimated to meet just over half of the annual 4.5 billion liters (4.5 MMT) of consumption.

Algeria continues to be one of the leading global dairy powder importers

TABLE 21 IMPORT – TOP EXPORTERS TO ALGERIA (TONS)

CHEESE		
	2021	2022
EU 27 External Trade (Brexit)	18,528	17,438
New Zealand	2,852	652
United Kingdom	657	333

BUTTER		
	2021	2022
New Zealand	3,343	1,964
Argentina	0	958
EU 27 External Trade (Brexit)	541	308
Uruguay	350	261
Turkey	8	11
Australia	353	0
Total	4,595	3,502
NON-FAT MILK POWDER		
	2021	2022
EU 27 External Trade (Brexit)	89,047	112,442
Turkey	18,666	18,191
New Zealand	0	12,056
Uruguay	6,018	10,178
Canada	4,766	6,704
Argentina	0	4,726
United Kingdom HMRC	5,331	3,25
United States	12,214	901
Ukraine	943	383
Switzerland	175	163
WHOLE MILK POWDER		
	2021	2022
New Zealand	47,145	113,693
Argentina	99,664	79,112
Uruguay	45,5	43,324
EU 27 External Trade (Brexit)	16,47	7,358
Brazil	5,232	3,928
United States	2,934	1,584
Malaysia	1,388	790
Turkey	475	0
Ukraine	400	0
United Kingdom	1,975	0

source : Data Aggregated from Trade Data Monitor, LLC

Argentina

Argentina's exports mainly concern cheese and butter. Among the project partners, the trade relationship with Algeria and Brazil.

TABLE 21 EXPORT - TOP IMPORTERS FROM ARGENTINA (TONS)

BUTTER		
	2021	2022
Russia	13,580	6,326
Saudi Arabia	-	1,775
Brazil	2,359	1,587
Algeria	-	958
Tunisia	-	675
Taiwan	-	233
Paraguay	-	20
CHEESE		
Brazil	22,775	26,320
Chile	15,876	18,203
Taiwan	1,148	2,882
Paraguay	2,628	2,284
Russia	7,203	2,126
Peru	866	1,535
Uruguay	808	1,243
U.S.A.	392	415
Bolivia	312	397

Source: HIS

In addition, Argentina imports cheese from Brazil, France and Italy.

TABLE 22 IMPORT - TOP EXPORTERS TO ARGENTINA (TONS)

CHEESE		
Uruguay	1,913	3,799
Brazil	523	550
France	72	39
Denmark	29	19
Italy	20	18
Spain	6	3
United Kingdom	9	3
Greece	3	3
Netherlands	-	1

Source: HIS

Brazil

Brazil's exports mainly concern cheese and among the project partners, the trade relationship with the United States and Argentina is significant.

TABLE 23 EXPORT - TOP IMPORTERS FROM BRAZIL (TONS)

CHEESE		
	2021	2022
Chile	1,133	938
U.S.A.	596	703

Argentina	619	603
Russia	836	503
Paraguay	400	370
Cuba	148	288
Taiwan	239	283
Perú	269	188
Uruguay	158	169
Angola	41	59

Source: HIS

Among the products highlighted, Brazil primarily imports butter and cheese. Among the partner countries, several relationships stand out, in particular with the three European and the two American countries.

TABLE 24 IMPORT - TOP EXPORTERS TO BRAZIL (TONS)

BUTTER		
Argentina	4,284	2,990
Uruguay	1,196	1,082
New Zealand	185	604
France	300	357
Italy	28	20
CHEESE		
	2021	2022
Argentina	22,597	26,308
Uruguay	7,038	5,179
Netherlands	731	623
France	904	465
Italy	406	414
United Kingdom	54	64
Germany	93	63
U.S.A.	53	35
Spain	39	20
Denmark	22	11

Source: HIS

France

Among the partner countries, France exports more products to Germany, Italy and U.S.A. Exported products vary and include butter, milk powder and cheese.

TABLE 25 EXPORT – TOP IMPORTERS FROM FRANCE (T)

BUTTER		
	2021	2022
Belgium	16,674	18,121
Korea, South	6,448	7,064
Netherlands	6,096	6,868

Italy	8,162	5,409
United Kingdom	5,876	6,110
Spain	4,930	5,144
China	5,236	5,530
Taiwan	3,306	3,569
Saudi Arabia	3,096	2,778
Japan	1,949	1,989
CHEESE		
	2021	2022
Germany	131,485	123,603
Netherlands	77,240	76,493
Spain	72,115	80,348
Belgium	78,800	75,012
United Kingdom	60,344	57,983
Italy	38,157	39,529
Luxembourg	32,897	38,267
U.S.A.	21,313	22,223
FAT- FILLED MILK POWDER		
	2021	2022
Spain	26,988	38,962
United Kingdom	39,750	39,007
Belgium	25,197	28,933
Italy	21,255	25,134
Germany	12,474	13,843
Netherlands	4,494	7,852
China	1,078	6,251
Nigeria	5,034	5,460
Iran	1,438	2,100
Ireland	3,687	4,387

Source: HIS

Germany

Among the partner countries, Germany exports more products to France and Italy, which are in the top 10.

TABLE 26 EXPORT – TOP IMPORTERS FROM GERMANY (TONS)

BUTTER		
	2021	2022
Netherlands	44,251	45,673
France	12,219	13,934
Austria	13,649	13,809
Italy	10,823	8,975
Belgium	8,159	7,530
Spain	4,664	3,708
Slovakia	6,973	6,508
Poland	8,941	8,522
Bulgaria	5,464	4,472

Denmark	3,595	4,264
CHEESE		
	2021	2022
Italy	242,872	236,467
Netherlands	184,728	174,519
Belgium	76,709	78,657
France	102,176	96,383
Spain	69,561	77,610
Austria	87,124	80,774
Romania	43,676	47,152
Czech Republic	46,772	41,507
United Kingdom	48,496	47,560
Greece	47,029	45,802
FAT- FILLED MILK POWDER		
	2021	2022
Netherlands	55,608	49,984
Poland	45,864	41,872
Austria	23,956	24,651
Italy	19,446	22,857
Belgium	15,245	16,863
Czech Republic	23,352	17,653
United Kingdom	8,427	11,522
France	20,536	16,591
Hungary	15,381	13,611
Spain	12,350	15,224

Source: HIS

Italy

Among the partner countries, Italy exports more products to Germany, France and the United States.

TABLE 27 TOP SEVEN IMPORTERS FROM ITALY (TONS)

BUTTER		
	2021	2022
Germany	2,955	1,428
Greece	1,207	1,229
Belgium	2,092	2,005
Spain	2,169	1,597
Austria	1,176	1,270
Poland	1,854	562
France	259	608
Croatia	229	378
S. Korea	829	612
CHEESE		
	2021	2022
France	115,649	127,118

Germany	83,200	76,319
United Kingdom	39,461	40,829
Spain	28,410	33,487
U.S.A.	37,351	36,698
Belgium	29,223	29,131
Switzerland	24,633	24,416
Netherlands	16,134	18,204
Austria	16,888	16,644
Poland	8,967	9,930
FAT- FILLED MILK POWDER		
	2021	2022
Australia	2,147	2,421
Belgium	2,621	3,716
Denmark	3,106	3,437
France	9,475	9,287
Germany	7,346	7,026
Poland	3,309	3,478
Spain	3,902	3,431
Sweden	3,010	2816
United Kingdom	7,273	6,925
U.S.A.	3,767	4,284

Source: ISTAT

South Africa

For South Africa, no specific data is available for each individual partner country, but the overall data for the respective product categories are given below.

TABLE 28 EXPORTS SOUTH AFRICA (TONS)

BUTTER		
	2021	2022
World	1,298	1,225
CHEESE		
	2021	2022
World	5,857	6,349

Source: IHS

TABLE 29 IMPORTS SOUTH AFRICA (TONS)

BUTTER		
	2021	2022
World	4,419	3,601
CHEESE		
	2021	2022
World	8,470	7,539

Source: IHS

United States of America

No project partner country is ranked within the U.S.A. major trade partners. The top five countries are listed for each product category investigated.

TABLE 30 TOP FIVE IMPORTERS FROM U.S.A (TONS)

BUTTER		
	2021	2022
Canada	17,131	35,315
Mexico	3,375	14,651
Bahrain	6,389	8,984
S. Korea	3,422	8,755
Saudi Arabia	4,901	2,031
FAT- FILLED MILK POWDER		
	2021	2022
Canada	87,984	91,529
Mexico	9,018	14,240
Ethiopia	8,003	12,036
Kenya	-	6,484
Nigeria	5,871	5,978
CHEESE		
	2021	2022
Mexico	104,858	123,684
S. Korea	69,406	75,811
Japan	41,244	48,426
Australia	24,967	28,782
Canada	15,730	17,732

Source: IHS

Zimbabwe

For Zimbabwe, no specific data is available for each individual partner country, but the overall data for the respective product categories are given below.

TABLE 31 EXPORTS ZIMBABWE (TONS)

BUTTER		
	2020	2021
World	0.45	303
CHEESE		
	2021	2022
World	150.83	59.95
WHOLE MILK POWDER		
	2021	2022
World	30	0

Source: IHS

TABLE 32 IMPORTS ZIMBABWE (TONS)

BUTTER		
	2020	2021
World	45.57	43.13
CHEESE		
	2021	2022
World	309	1,076
WHOLE MILK POWDER		
	2021	2022
World	1,960	5,147

Source: IHS

Trade tariffs - dairy

The table below shows the average import rates (as a percentage) for dairy products recorded by the selected countries in trade flows with trading partners. The table shows the *Final Bound Duties* and (MFN) *Most favoured nation* applied duties. Looking at the average of the MFN applied duties the highest import tariffs are applied by EU countries (38.4%) and Zimbabwe (40.3%). Much lower are the import tariffs in other countries in most of the cases around 20%, the lowest rate is applied by South Africa (6.8%).

TABLE 33 IMPORT TARIFFS IN UE AND IN SELECTED COUNTRIES IN 2022

DAIRY PRODUCTS	FINAL BOUND DUTIES				MFN APPLIED DUTIES		
	AVG	Duty free in %	Max	Binding in %	AVG	Duty free in %	Max
Algeria	<i>nr</i>	<i>nr</i>	<i>nr</i>	<i>nr</i>	22,7	0	30
Argentina	35	0	35	100	18,3	0	28
Brazil	48,8	0	55	100	16	0	28
UE	42,4	0	146	100	38,4	0	133
South Africa	92,3	0	96	100	6,8	23,8	17
USA	17,9	0,3	81	100	19,6	0,3	81
Zimbabwe	150	0	150	100	40,3	4,8	150

Source: WTO

Trade tariffs - beef

The table below shows the average import rates (as a percentage) for animal products, including beef products, recorded by the selected countries in trade flows with trading partners. The table shows the Final Bound Duties and (MFN) Most favoured nation applied duties. Looking at the average of the MFN applied duties the highest import tariff is applied by Morocco (69.1%). Much lower are the import tariffs in other countries, in most of the cases around 10%, in the UE the average import tariff is 17%, the lowest rate is applied by USA (2.3%).

TABLE 34 AVERAGE IMPORT RATES (%)

ANIMAL PRODUCTS	FINAL BOUND DUTIES				MFN APPLIED DUTIES		
	AVG	Duty free in %	Max	Binding in %	AVG	Duty free in %	Max
Argentina	26,5	0	35	100	8,3	6,5	16
Brazil	37,8	5,4	55	100	6,4	17,4	13
UE	19,1	24,3	118	100	17	28,2	118
Morocco	94,5	0	289	100	69,1	0	200
Namibia	37,4	30,6	160	100	10,9	61,1	82
South Africa	37,4	30,6	160	100	10,9	61,1	82
USA	2,4	30,8	26	100	2,3	30,5	26

Source: WTO

Data pool on environmental and social sustainability standards relevant for agricultural trade

The MATS project closely links trade with the concept of sustainability in terms of economic, environmental and social sustainability and the associated SDGs. It is necessary to remember that each sustainability dimension must be satisfied, otherwise sustainability is not comprehensively and authentically addressed. The case studies on which this deliverable D3.4. is based have been associated with the following SDGs, as they deal with topics related to the SDGs.

Case Study N.º 3	Case Study N.º10	Case Study N.º11	Case Study N.º13
<i>Trade, sustainability and environmental linkages in Finnish dairy production</i>	<i>Beef and policy coherence for sustainable development</i>	<i>Private standards and sustainable trade</i>	<i>Dairy production, standards and competitiveness in global markets</i>

In addressing the role of the SDGs in the case studies, reference is also made to *Table 35* of the [D2.4 of the project](#), which highlights for each Goal the indicators chosen to create greater comparability between the different case studies analysed. The indicators selected represent the dimensions of sustainable development and are subject to variations depending on the case study. The social sustainability aspect is a primary focus in three case studies covered in this paper (CS 10/11/13), which in fact fall within the action area of Goals n.º 1, 2, 3, 6. The social aspect was also partially analysed for case study n.º 3, which focuses more on the environmental component (goals n.º13 and 15).

TABLE 35 MATS D2.4

	SDG #	MULTI-COUNTRY TRADE FOCUS				NATIONAL PRODUCTION FOCUS							PRODUCTION OUTCOMES FOCUS				#
		CS4	CS10	CS14	CS15	CS1	CS2	CS6	CS7	CS8	CS11	CS12	CS13	CS3	CS5	CS9	
Social dimension																	
Ownership rights	5.a.1			X				X	X	X	X						5
Social Protection	1.3.1							X	X	X	X						5
Discrimination	10.3.1	X				X		X							X		4
Unemployment rates	8.5.2	X			X		X		X			X				X	6
Human rights (Child labour, forced labour)	8.7.1	X															1
Working conditions	8.3.1		X	X	X		X	X	X			X				X	8
	8.8.2		X	X			X	X	X		X	X					8
Human dimension																	
Poverty rates	1.1.1		X	X	X	X		X	X	X		X			X	X	11
Access to basic services	1.4.1	X							X	X							3
Food security and nutrition (e.g., famine, nutrition, food quality)	2.1.1					X		X	X					X			4
	2.1.2				X	X								X			3
	2.2.2					X								X			2
	3.9.1								X								1
Health	3.9.2	X							X								2
	3.8.1																0
Economy and Markets																	
Volume traded	17.11.1	X	X	X	X	X			X		X	X	X				9
Prices (unit value, distortions...)	2.c.1							X						X			2
Income creation	8.5.1						X							X			2
	2.3.2		X		X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X			10
Subsidies & tariff lines	12.c.1								X								1
	10.a.1																0
Production	2.3.1	X		X			X		X		X	X	X			X	9
	2.4.1	X		X			X	X	X					X		X	5
	12.3.1					X	X						X	X			4
Value added (GDP)	8.1.1				X												1
	8.2.1																0
Natural capital																	
Exposure to extreme climatic events	13.1.1	X															1
Access to environment-friendly technology	17.7.1						X		X							X	3
Natural resource use	6.4.1																0
	6.4.2	X		X									X				3
	7.2.1													X			0
	8.4.1		X	X	X			X				X	X				6
GHG emissions	13.2.2		X	X	X				X				X				4
Water-related ecosystems	6.6.1			X													1
	11.3.1			X				X		X							3
Water pollution	15.1.1	X								X							2
	3.9.2	X								X							1
	6.3.2	X															1
Soil erosion	15.3.1							X									1
Policy, governance & regulations																	
Legal Framework	5.1.1	X			X			X	X	X	X	X					7
Public revenues and expenditure (agriculture sector, essential services, pro-poor, and conservation/ biodiversity)	2.a.1		X			X	X					X		X		X	6
	2.a.2	X	X			X	X					X	X		X		7
	2.b.1	X	X		X	X						X					7
	1.a.2				X		X		X	X							4
	1.b.1							X	X								2
	15.a.1					X					X						2

Source: Deliverable 2.4 MATS

Social sustainability

In an attempt to increase the sustainability of agricultural trade, it is necessary to assess more specifically the sustainability of production processes in the agri-food chain and it is essential not to neglect the component of positive and negative social impacts. If the requirements of social sustainability are met, trade can be more sustainable.

In order to achieve a more comprehensive understanding of sustainability in relation to agricultural trade, the social sustainability dimension must be explicitly addressed in the product value chain. A useful transverse *indicator* for analysing the human and social dimension is 8.8.2, which concerns working conditions.

Given the complexity of the topic, it was deemed insufficient to rely on a single indicator or on a small pool of indicators that have a very strong theoretical basis, but little applicability to individual case studies.

For this reason, it was deemed appropriate to make an effort to translate from the known *SDGs* to the more operational disclosures of the *GRI* system. The **GRI Standards** -*Global Reporting Initiative Standards*- represent a globally widely used best practice also in the agri-food sectors, for reporting publicly on a range of economic, environmental and social impacts.¹² Sustainability reporting based on the Standards provides information about an organization's (in this case it is applied to Country legislation) positive or negative contributions to sustainable development. These standards are characterised by being practice-oriented and have provided a guide for the compilation of a database enclosing working conditions in different countries, specifically for applications in MATS (Langeneck L., Steiner B., 2022).

The social impact analysis was based on the study of working conditions in the case study countries. This approach allows us to first investigate the efforts made by each state to promote development-oriented policies that support productive activities, decent job creation, entrepreneurship, creativity

¹² "The *GRI Standards* are the world's most widely used standards for sustainability reporting. They have been widely adopted by leading companies in more than 100 countries, and are referenced in policy instruments and stock exchange guidance around the world."
<https://www.globalreporting.org/media/wmxlklns/about-gri-brochure-2022.pdf>

and innovation, and encourage the formalization and growth of micro, small and medium-sized enterprises, including through access to financial services (sub-objective 8.3 of SDGs), for example, by ensuring formal employment (indicator 8.3.1).

At the same time, it is crucial to protect labour rights and promote safe and secure working environments for all workers, including migrant workers, in particular women migrants, and those in precarious employment (sub goal 8.8).

In order to try to understand the level of national compliance with labour rights (freedom of association and collective bargaining, indicator 8.8.2) and the consistency between national legislations and the market dynamics, the choice fell to going to research for each state engaged in the case study the type of existing legislation regarding labour standardization.

For this purpose, a database was built to collect and compare different countries and understand the dynamics of the trade mechanism through the partner network.

Data were collected from the main official government websites and available public databases.

The tool used to construct the database is Excel. As the contracts in the respective countries were read and studied, additional sections and categories were added, and at the end, those not representative for this cross-sectional analysis were removed.

The data reported refer to the most up-to-date data available for collective bargaining agreements, and where these were not available or exhaustive, reference was made to the more generic national Labour Code. The States surveyed are Algeria, Argentina, Brazil, Finland, France, Germany, Kenya, Italy, Morocco, Namibia, South Africa, the United States of America, and Zimbabwe.

The database is divided into several parts and each of these is divided into a multitude of sections that provide detailed information.

In each of the specific parts, crucial information was gathered to understand the negative and positive impacts of labour on social and marketing dynamics. This study made it possible to analyse similarities and differences that can make an exchange more 'convenient' (lower prices, but at what cost?) or more

'competitive' (importance of product and process quality, qualified personnel, etc.).

However, it is to be noted that although the analysis has attempted to achieve a high degree of detail, it is not possible to fully represent a world made up of exceptions, special cases and realities that very often differ from what is desired on paper (child labour, exploitation, undeclared work). Nevertheless, this work could be useful in defining the point at which the country protects its workers.

At the end of this section, it is possible to find a summary table (Table 31) with the translation (mapping) of the SDGs into the GRI system.

The data collected, classified and mapped within this data pool D3.4. are useful for other tasks of the MAT'S project and are intended to be implemented in different phases. The data has been used will be used for consortium and workshop meetings where matters of MATS case study comparability is discussed on social and environmental sustainability standards. The output will feed into D3.5 *Summary report on case study results*, as well as D3.6 *Discussion paper on sustainability standards and competitiveness*. Furthermore, it connects our Analytical framework D2.4., where it is important to have data comparability, coherence and integration. For example, within mathematical models that can highlight the cause-effect relationships of phenomena (e.g., the causal loop diagram methodology, CLDs), the data identified and classified here will be employed. Furthermore, having a large amount of data identified, classified and harmonized allows the possibility of recounting some possible scenarios occurring within a given sector/trade, as it is done via the CGE models within MATS (see also the forthcoming D3.3 *Report and Policy Brief on the results of the integrated model-based assessment*).

General background – social sustainability

Collective bargaining is a constant in the legislation of the different partner countries, although in different ways. For example, collective agreements can be made at the organization, a particular site, the industry level, or at the national level in countries where this is the practice. Moreover, consultation has not always been possible, since in some cases they are not published, as is the case in Germany.

In most cases, contracts do not have an expiry date but are updated periodically. According to the *GRI 407-1 "Freedom of Association and Collective Bargaining (2016)"*, collective agreements can cover specific groups of workers, for example, those performing a specific activity or working at a specific location.

An organization is expected to respect the rights of workers to exercise freedom of association and collective bargaining. It is also expected to not benefit from or contribute to such violations through its business relationships (e.g., suppliers).

The column labelled *Links* shows the connections to the main sources used. The first choice always goes over collective agreements when present, which are supplemented with national standards when they do not cover precise aspects and replaced with labour codes when necessary.

Please, note that each time the cell reports "*not specified*", means that the particular information is not describe in the national/collective agreement but should be negotiated between the parties and included in the contract of employment.

TABLE 36 DATABASE, GENERAL INFORMATION

SDG Indicator 8.8.2 GRI Disclosure 407-1			
COUNTRY	NATIONAL AGREEMENT or collective labour agreement	LINK	Presence of collective agreements
ALGERIA Dairy CS13	<i>Loi n° 90-11 du 21 Avril 1990</i> Relative aux relations de travail, modifiée et complétée	Link to Algeria	Yes
ARGENTINA Dairy CS13 Beef CS10	<i>Ley de Contrato de Trabajo</i>	Link to Argentina	Yes
BRAZIL Dairy CS13 Beef CS10	<i>Consolidação das Leis do Trabalho</i>	Link to Brazil	Yes, but usually they use a "Carteira de Trabalho e Previdência Social - CTPS"
FRANCE Dairy CS13 Beef CS10)	<i>"Convention Collective nationale proction agricole/CUMA du 15 Septembre 2020"</i>	Link to France	Yes
GERMANY Dairy CS13 Beef CS10	Absence of a separate labour law code. Labour law is governed by several laws: <i>das Arbeitszeitgesetz (ArbZG); das Bundesurlaubsgesetz (BUrlG); das Entgeltfortzahlungsgesetz (EntgFG); das Teilzeit- und Befristungsgesetz (TzBfG); Das Bürgerliche Gesetzbuch (BGB), that regulates the notice period.</i>	das Arbeitszeitgesetz (ArbZG) - Law on working time das Bundesurlaubsgesetz (BUrlG) - Law on minimum leave for employees das Entgeltfortzahlungsgesetz (EntgFG) - Law on payment of remuneration on public holidays and in the event of sickness das Teilzeit- und Befristungsgesetz (TzBfG) - Law on part-time work and fixed-term contracts Das Bürgerliche Gesetzbuch (BGB) - civil code	Collective agreements between the employers' association/union and agreements between employer/works council are not available for consultation and are not national contracts.
ITALY Dairy CS13 Beef CS10	<i>"Contratto collettivo nazionale di lavoro per gli operai agricoli e florovivaisti"</i>	Link to Italy	Yes
MOROCCO Beef CS10	<i>Code du travail</i>	Link to Morocco	Yes
NAMIBIA Beef CS10	<i>Labour Act</i>	Link to Namibia	Yes
SOUTH AFRICA Dairy CS13 Beef CS10	<i>"Basic Conditions of Employment Act, nr 75 of 1997 and the Sectoral Determination 13: Farm Worker Sector "</i>	Link to South Africa	Yes
U.S.A. Dairy CS13 Beef CS10	<i>Fair Labour Standards Act (FLSA) Wage and Hour Division (WHD)</i>	Link to USA	Yes, but only in certain sectors
ZIMBABWE Dairy CS13	<i>Labour Act (28:01)</i>	Link to Zimbabwe	Yes
FINLAND Dairy CS3	<i>"Collective agreement for agricultural workers"</i>	Link to Finland	Yes
KENYA Avocado CS11	<i>Employment Act, 2007</i> <i>Collective bargaining agreement (ex. Members of the Sisal Growers and employers' association (Kenya)- the Kenya plantation and agricultural WORKERS' UNION</i>	Link to Kenya	Yes

Working time

The daily, weekly or monthly working hours vary widely depending on the type of contract and the country concerned. In some cases, the value entered refers to the hours defined by the national labour code, while in many other cases, the value from collective bargaining is given, which must always be equal to or better than the national value. The calculation of working hours per day is also significant with regard to the risk of accidents and the occurrence of work-related illnesses.

Typically, in most countries, working hours in the agricultural sector range from 7 to 9 a day. Daily working hours can reach a maximum of 10 hours, but in this case, it is considered overtime and paid with an increase in basic salary. Among the partner countries, Zimbabwe is the country with the greatest variation, with up to 10 hours of daily work as a rule.

The agricultural sector also has the particularity of providing, in many contractual cases, for the possibility of increasing daily working hours in periods of seasonality and workload, on condition that a maximum limit is not exceeded and with the guarantee of being able to compensate in a period of lower load.

TABLE 37 WORKING TIME

SDGs indicator 8.8.2						
GRI 401 disclosure 2						
GRI 401 disclosure 2						
COUNTRY	WORKING TIME per week	WORKING TIME per day	Overtime	WEEKLY REST	VACATION	NATIONAL HOLIDAYS (No.)
ALGERIA <i>Dairy CS13</i>	44-48 h	8-9 h	<i>Not specified</i>	Each Friday	30 d/year	11 da
ARGENTINA <i>Dairy CS13</i> <i>Beef CS10</i>	40-48 h	8 h	3 h/d 30 h/month 200 h/ year	35 h starting at 1 p.m. on Saturdays	14-35 d/year	13 d
BRAZIL <i>Dairy CS13</i> <i>Beef CS10</i>	40-44 h	8 h	2 h/d	Each Sunday	12-30 d/year	12 d
FRANCE <i>Dairy CS13</i> <i>Beef CS10</i>	35 h	7-10 h	<i>Not specified</i>	Each Sunday	30 d/year	11 d
GERMANY <i>Dairy CS13</i> <i>Beef CS10</i>	40 h	8-10 h	8 h/week	Each Sunday	20-24 d/year	10-13 d/year
ITALY <i>Dairy CS13</i> <i>Beef CS10</i>	39 h	7 h	5 h/d 85 h/week	Each Sunday	26 days/year	13 d
MOROCCO <i>Beef CS10</i>	46 h	10 h	<i>Not specified*</i> <i>*Max working time 2,496 h/year</i>	Each Friday or Saturday, or Sunday, according to the weekly market	18 d/year	11 d
NAMIBIA <i>Beef CS10</i>	45 h	8-9 h	3 h/d 10 h/week	36 h, starting at 12 am on Saturday	28 d/year	12 d
SOUTH AFRICA <i>Dairy CS13</i> <i>Beef CS10</i>	40 h	8 h	2 h/d 12 h/week	36 h, starting at 12 am on Saturday	21 d/year	12 d
U.S.A. <i>Dairy CS13</i> <i>Beef CS10</i>	40 h	8 h	<i>Not specified</i>	<i>Each Sunday</i>	14-25 d/year	12 d
ZIMBABWE <i>Dairy CS13</i>	52 h	10 h	<i>Not specified</i>	24 h of rest each week	¹ / ₁₂ of his qualifying service in each year of employment, (max 90 d)	11 d
FINLAND <i>Dairy CS3</i>	40 h	8 h	2 h/d 10 h/week	35 h, usually Sundays	24 d/year	8 d
KENYA <i>Avocado CS11</i>	46 h (6 days)	-	10 h/week	At least one rest day in every period of seven days	21 d/year	10 d

Education

Education is a transversal concept that can cover many areas and modalities. For example, it is relevant to plan education on human rights and working conditions that must be guaranteed, to recognise and condemn the use of force, inhuman and degrading treatment, discrimination, identification and registration.

In some cases, it is explicit in the contract that employees can take additional leave to finish or continue their studies, even outside the work context and sphere.

Employee training represents an investment on the part of the employer who in this way has a qualified and more competitive workforce at his disposal.

In some states there is a professional training plan that is repeated on a cadenced basis with the aim of elevating the knowledge and skills of employees. One example is a periodic evaluation every two years as is the case in France and the possibility of advancing in professional "level". Regular performance and career development reviews can also enhance employee satisfaction, which correlates with improved organizational performance.

In order to guarantee the right of training and education, some guidelines for the employer must be assured at the regulatory level:

- recognition of all types of vocational training and instruction.
- paid educational leave provided by an organization for its employees.
- training or education pursued externally and paid for in whole or in part by an organization.
- training on specific topics.

TABLE 38 EDUCATION

	SDGs Indicator 8.8.2	
	GRI 403 disclosure 5 GRI 404 disclosure 1, 2, 3	
COUNTRY	PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT	LEVELS (NQF)
ALGERIA <i>Dairy CS13</i>	Leave is provided to enable the employee to attend professional courses authorised by the employer and to take academic or professional examinations.	<i>Not specified</i>
ARGENTINA <i>Dairy CS13</i> <i>Beef CS10</i>	2 d (consecutive) for educational examinations, max 10 d/year	<i>Not specified</i>
BRAZIL <i>Dairy CS13</i> <i>Beef CS10</i>	Paid by Workers' Support Fund (FAT) for professional and technological training	<i>Not specified</i>
FRANCE <i>Dairy CS13</i> <i>Beef CS10</i>	Workers have an individual account of credits for continuing education, lasting all their working life (Compte Personnel de Formation). Workers accumulate 500 h of training in the CPF, with max 150 h per year	6-12
GERMANY <i>Dairy CS13</i> <i>Beef CS10</i>	Workers can take educational leave to attend trainings (e.g., citizenship education, language courses and vocational training)	<i>Not specified</i>
ITALY <i>Dairy CS13</i> <i>Beef CS10</i>	200 paid h/3 years 150 h/3 years (remedial courses)	3
MOROCCO <i>Beef CS10</i>	Workers can attend continuing education courses	<i>Not specified</i>
NAMIBIA <i>Beef CS10</i>	<i>Not specified</i>	<i>Not specified</i>
SOUTH AFRICA <i>Dairy CS13</i> <i>Beef CS10</i>	<i>Not specified</i>	8
U.S.A. <i>Dairy CS13</i> <i>Beef CS10</i>	<i>Not specified</i>	<i>Not specified</i>
ZIMBABWE <i>Dairy CS13</i>	<i>Not specified</i>	10
FINLAND <i>Dairy CS3</i>	<i>Not specified</i>	<i>Not specified</i>
KENYA <i>Avocado CS11</i>	<i>Not specified</i>	<i>Not specified</i>

Paid leave

The number and type of leaves reserved for different categories of workers are among the most highly variable values in the countries analysed. This component is strongly influenced by the type of society in which it is contextualised. The data collected within this database refer to the working conditions related to a full-time worker. This screening was done with the intention of ensuring sufficient homogeneity in the data, making them more comparable. Given this premise, it is necessary to point out that many of the benefits are reserved exclusively for full-time employees and not for temporary or part/time workers.

According to **GRI 401-2-3**, some of these benefits are included in the welfare-related components that will be reported later, such as life insurance and health care. Among the benefits covered in this Disclosure there are leave, the following are the best known:

- marriage leaves
- maternity and paternity leave
- Death of relatives
- Parental leave
- Leave for remedial course (cross indicator with “education” section)

All these benefits for full-time employees are a key factor in retaining employees.

Substantial differences can be observed particularly in the sections on maternity/paternity leave and parental leave. In fact, many countries have introduced legislation to provide parental leave with the aim of allowing employees to take leave and return to work in the same (or a comparable) position. The application of legislation varies according to interpretation by government, employers and employees.

Many women are discouraged from taking leave and returning to work by employer practices that affect their employment security, remuneration and career path, as many men are not encouraged to take the leave to which they are entitled. Equitable gender choice for maternity and paternity leave, and other leave entitlements, can lead to the greater recruitment and retention of qualified employees and it can also boost employee morale and productivity. Men’s uptake of paternity leave options can indicate the degree to which an organization encourages fathers to take such leave. Men taking advantage of

leave entitlements positively impacts women to take such leave without prejudicing their career path. (Source: GRI 401-3)

TABLE 39 PAID LEAVE

SDGs indicator 8.8.2						
GRI 401 disclosure 2, 3						
GRI 404 disclosure 1						
COUNTRY	MARRIAGE LEAVE	MATERNITY LEAVE	PATERNITY LEAVE	DEATH OF RELATIVES	PARENTAL LEAVE	Others
ALGERIA <i>Dairy CS13</i>	3 d	98 d	2 d	3 d	<i>Not specified</i>	<i>Not specified</i>
ARGENTINA <i>Dairy CS13</i> <i>Beef CS10</i>	10 d	-can be extended 3-6 months without pay	2 d	3 d	<i>Not specified</i>	<i>Not specified</i>
BRAZIL <i>Dairy CS13</i> <i>Beef CS10</i>	3 d	120-180 d -can be extended to 6	5 d <u>Adoption</u> : 5 d	<i>Not specified</i>	<i>Not specified</i>	<i>Not specified</i>
FRANCE <i>Dairy CS13</i> <i>Beef CS10</i>	4 d	80-130 d (According to the no. of children) <u>Multiple born</u> : 170-230 d	11 d <u>Multiple born</u> : 18 d +30 d in case of hospitalisation	3 d 7 d in case of death of a child	3-5 d/year (According to the age of the child) Not paid	<i>Not specified</i>
GERMANY <i>Dairy CS13</i> <i>Beef CS10</i>	<i>Not specified</i>	100 d	<i>Not specified</i>	2 d	10 d	<i>Not specified</i>
ITALY <i>Dairy CS13</i> <i>Beef CS10</i>	15 d	100 d	10 d	3 d	2-3 d	<i>Not specified</i>
MOROCCO <i>Beef CS10</i>	4 d (only 2 d paid)	70 d	3 d	3 d (only 1 d paid)	<i>Not specified</i>	<i>Not specified</i>
NAMIBIA <i>Beef CS10</i>	<i>Not specified</i>	60 d (After at least 6 months of continuous employment)	<i>Not specified</i>	5 d	<i>Not specified</i>	<i>Not specified</i>
SOUTH AF- RICA <i>Dairy CS13</i> <i>Beef CS10</i>	<i>Not specified</i>	4 consecutive months	10 d	<i>Not specified</i>	10 d + 3 d on request	<i>Not specified</i>
U.S.A. <i>Dairy CS13</i> <i>Beef CS10</i>	<i>Not specified</i>	60 d (After at least 12 months of continuous employment) to take care of parents, spouse, minor/dependent child who has a serious health condition.		Defined by each state	60 d (After at least 12 months of continuous employment) to take care of parents, spouse, minor/dependent child who has a serious health condition.	Workers are allowed to leave with pay for jury duty or to perform other civil duties. Military training leave with pay is permitted to a max of 21 d/year. Leave to enter military service, U.S. Peace Corps or U.S. Public Health Service: permitted but without pay.
ZIMBABWE <i>Dairy CS13</i>	12 d (Special leave of covering)	98 d	12 d (Special leave of covering several reasons)	12 d (Special leave of covering several reasons)	12 d (Special leave of covering several reasons)	<i>Not specified</i>

	several reasons)					
FINLAND <i>Dairy CS3</i>	1 d	105 d of which 30 d paid (or 158 d divided between the parents as they see fit, not paid by the employer but social benefits received from the government)	54 d or 158 d divided between parents, not paid by the employer but social benefits received from government	1 d	in case of illness of children under the age of 10, 1-4 days of paid leave (sudden illness of elderly parent entitles a leave for making the required arrangements)	<i>Not specified</i>
KENYA <i>Avocado CS11</i>	<i>Not specified</i>	3 months	Two weeks	<i>Not specified</i>	<i>Not specified</i>	<i>Not specified</i>

Occupational health and safety

Concerning *health in the workplace*, contracts refer to work illnesses and injury in the workplace as dangers to be prevented. To accomplish this, it is essential to understand which activities and factors the worker is exposed to and which pose risks in the short or long term.

Referring again to the GRI methodology, it is important to observe which States carry out prevention or compensation activities. The former includes short time working and high shift work. In some cases, there is also an increase in basic pay, sometimes exclusively in terms of compensation. The work-related hazards that pose a risk of ill health and of workplace injury (for example the heavy and harmful work) (*GRI 403-09* and *GRI 403-10*). To avoid this risk, the employer made different actions for prevents as a reduced working hours, high turnover or extra pay are the most frequently used 'solutions'. Only France, Namibia and Kenya leave the decision of the management of the harmful works to the relation between employee and employer. In all the other case the national/collective law require a system of prevention based on “planning activities, do, verify and correct”.

Usually a reduction in hours (and thus a higher staff turnover) is opted for, sometimes accompanied by the payment of an extra share on the basic salary. The aim is to expose the worker to as little danger as possible and to increase his or her compensation. In some countries, as is the situation in Italy, training courses are provided for all employees so that they can learn in more detail about the risks and possible behaviour.

TABLE 40 HEALTH AND SAFETY

SDGs indicator 8.8.2				
GRI 202 disclosure 2				
GRI 403 disclosure 1-2-3-4-5-6-7-8-9-10				
COUNTRY	ILLNESS AND WORKPLACE INJURY (also work-related ill health)	PAY IN CASE OF ILLNESS	PAY IN CASE OF WORKPLACE INJURY	HEAVY AND HARMFUL WORK
ALGERIA <i>Dairy CS13</i>	Sick leave: employees must present relevant documents as proof of their illness.	Paid from the first day of illness.	<i>Not specified</i>	Reductions in working hours
ARGENTINA <i>Dairy CS13</i> <i>Beef CS10</i>	The employment is guaranteed for the duration of the sick leave.	3-12 months full paid sick leave <i>(According to the employee's seniority and family status)</i> +12 months (not paid) if recovery does not take place	- <u>Total permanent disability</u> : monthly allowance [(salary*53) *65/age at the onset of disability] + ARS 2,000 (EUR 6.70) - <u>Partial permanent disability</u> : depending on the degree of disability (flat rate) - disability 50-66%: ARS 80,000 (EUR 266) + disability percentage* ARS 180,000 (600 euro) - Disability < 50%: [(salary * 53) * 65/age at the onset of disability] - <u>Temporary disability</u> : 100% salary - <u>Death</u> : dependants' compensation equal to the permanent disability, plus an additional fixed allowance of ARS 120,000.	Reductions in working hours
BRAZIL <i>Dairy CS13</i> <i>Beef CS10</i>	Temporary illness does not require a minimum contribution Sickness or disability compensation after at least 12 months of employment	- temporary illness: - <15 d sick leave: 50% salary - > 15 d sick leave: 91% salary - permanent disability: 100% salary + 25% in case of need of continuous care		Increase of salary +30%
FRANCE <i>Dairy CS13</i> <i>Beef CS10</i>	<i>Not specified</i>	- daily allowance: 50% basic daily salary - monthly allowance: total last three gross salaries / 91.25	- daily allowance: 50% basic daily salary - monthly allowance: total last three gross salaries / 91.25	<i>Not specified</i>
GERMANY <i>Dairy CS13</i> <i>Beef CS10</i>	Employment guaranteed for 6 weeks, renewable for other 6 weeks.	≤6 weeks: full salary > 6 weeks: 70-90% salary	<i>Not specified</i>	Prevention: minimization of exposure and specific training
ITALY <i>Dairy CS13</i> <i>Beef CS10</i>	the employment is guaranteed for 180 d Oncological pathology: + 6 months (not paid) Workplace injury: employment is guaranteed until complete recovery, (max 12 month)	Min 80% of baseline salary	80% salary	-Reduction of the length of the shifts -Increase of salary - Prevention: specific training
MOROCCO <i>Beef CS10</i>	Illness or accident must be notified and justified to the employer within 48 h.	180 d sick leave	Temporary disability: 100% salary	Increase of salary

		>180 d or inability to work: the employee can be resigned from work		
NAMIBIA Beef CS10	30-36 d <i>(According to the no. of working days per week).</i>	<i>Not specified</i>	<i>Not specified</i>	<i>Not specified</i>
SOUTH AFRICA Dairy CS13 Beef CS10	10 d/year The employees must notify as soon as possible in case of absence for illness	<i>Not specified</i>	<i>Not specified</i>	<i>Not specified</i>
U.S.A. Dairy CS13 Beef CS10	60 d for serious illness (After at least 12 months of continuous employment)	<i>Not specified</i>	<i>Not specified</i>	<i>Not specified</i>
ZIMBABWE Dairy CS13	<i>Not specified</i>	Max 90 d (full pay)		<i>Not specified</i>
FINLAND Dairy CS3	Paid leave for 2 d on personal notice after which a doctoral consultation is needed	<i>Not specified</i>	<i>Not specified</i>	An extra pay of 52 cents/hour is paid for "dirty" work
KENYA Avocado CS11	<i>Not specified</i>	min. sick leave 7 d with full pay and then sick leave of 7 d with 1/2 pay	<i>Not specified</i>	<i>Not specified</i>

Social Welfare

Welfare is realised in different ways and has many facets that vary greatly depending on the country we are in. **GRI 403-6** refers to the promotion of employers' health outside the purely work environment, for example by facilitating workers' access to extra-occupational health and medical services. Increasing health coverage, even making it universal as stipulated in SDG n.º 3, plays a key role in ensuring people's well-being, without which there can be no talk of social sustainability or even sustainability in the broader sense.

Welfare refers to all measures that are recognized at the National level and applied at the farm level to ensure and increase the wellbeing of the employee. as mentioned earlier in the section on education, in welfare, a number of benefits are guaranteed which increase retention and, in the long term, the productivity and efficiency of the employee.

Highly variable, for example, is the type of policy inherent in retirement and minimum age. It is interesting here to note that in many countries where the minimum retirement age is relatively low, life expectancy is also extremely limited. We can observe this context particularly in African countries.

TABLE 41 SOCIAL WELFARE

SDG: Indicator 8.8.2				
	GRI 201 disclosure 1 GRI 403 disclosure 6	GRI 401 disclosure 2	GRI 201 disclosure 3	GRI 401 disclosure 2
COUNTRY	SOCIAL SERVICES AND INSURANCE	UNEMPLOYMENT BENEFITS	SUPPLEMENTARY HEALTH CARE FUND	CONDITIONS OF RETIREMENT
ALGERIA <i>Dairy CS13</i>	<i>Not specified</i>	<i>Not specified</i>	<i>Not specified</i>	Not specified in this law
ARGENTINA <i>Dairy CS13</i> <i>Beef CS10</i>	Workers benefit of a health care plan financed by contributions through deductions of salary, both by worker and employer. Death, illness and disability are covered by a specific and compulsory insurance.	<u>Conditions:</u> Min 6 months of contributions in the 3 years before unemployment. <u>Duration:</u> unemployment benefits can be granted from 2 to 12 months, depending on the number of contribution months.	-employer contribution: 6% of salary -worker contribution: 3% of salary An additional contribution of 1.5% of salary is paid by the worker for each beneficiary covered by the health plan.	min 65 years (men) or 60 (women) of age + min 30 years of contribution
BRAZIL <i>Dairy CS13</i> <i>Beef CS10</i>	The Brazilian Federation of Workers' Unions (<i>Central Unica dos Trabalhadores</i>) supports workers to obtain guaranteed medical care. However, most of the workers do not have an employment contract, so they cannot profit of the association's support and guaranteed medical care.	<u>Conditions:</u> Min 6 months of contributions in the 3 years before unemployment.	-employer contribution: 12% of salary -worker contribution: 8-11% of salary	-min 65 years (men) or 60 (women) of age Amount: 70% of average salary + gradual increases every 12 months
FRANCE <i>Dairy CS13</i> <i>Beef CS10</i>	Benefits are financed by compulsory contributions paid by employers, employees, as well as by deductions from the state budget. The social service helps you manage the impact of personal or professional difficulties related to your state of health.	Tot. no. of wages received over the 24-36 months* the no. of days corresponding to the duration of the wage, i.e., the days worked and not worked over the 24-36-month period. The number of calendar days between the beginning of the first contract and the end of the last is then considered.	<i>Not specified</i>	<i>Min 64 years</i> earlier is possible in case of illness or disability. From the age of 70, your employer can retire you automatically, without your consent.
GERMANY <i>Dairy CS13</i> <i>Beef CS10</i>	Workers benefit of a social security plan financed by contributions through deductions of salary, both by worker and employer. Death,	<u>Conditions:</u> -Min 12 months of contributions in the 3 years before unemployment - application to the Employment Agency as a job seeker <u>Duration:</u>	-employer contribution depends on the surface of the farm and its income	- 67 years of age or -min 45 years of contribution Education (up to 8 years), raising children (up to 3 years per child) or care of relatives are

	unemployment, illness, accidents at work, occupational diseases and disability are covered by a specific and compulsory insurance.	According to worker's age <u>Amount:</u> 60%-67% last salary		also considered as qualifying contributory time periods.
ITALY Dairy CS13 Beef CS10	Workers benefit of a social security plan, which also covers accidents, illness, invalidity and involuntary unemployment	Min 1.352,19 EUR	There is a specific Agricultural Fund which provides supplementary public assistance services for health, safety and social purposes. Employer contribution: 51 euro/worker/year	- 67 years of age or - min 42 years and 10 months (men) and 41 years and 10 months (women) of contribution
MOROCCO Beef CS10	<i>Not specified</i>	<i>Not specified</i>	The user company is responsible for insuring its employees against accidents at work and occupational diseases.	60 years
NAMIBIA Beef CS10	<i>Not specified</i>	<i>Not specified</i>	<i>Not specified</i>	<i>Not specified</i>
SOUTH AFRICA Dairy CS13 Beef CS10	<i>Not specified</i>	There is an Unemployment Insurance Fund financed by the employer.	<i>Not specified</i>	<i>Not specified</i>
U.S.A. Dairy CS13 Beef CS10	Eligible employees and their families are covered by medical, dental and vision insurance. Eligible employees are provided with basic term life insurance and may purchase supplemental insurance. Eligible employees receive basic Long-Term Disability (LTD) coverage.	<i>Not specified</i>	<i>Not specified</i>	Each State defines minimum conditions
ZIMBABWE Dairy CS13	<i>Not specified</i>	<i>Not specified</i>	<i>Not specified</i>	An employee who reaches the age of sixty years may be required by the employer to retire.
FINLAND Dairy CS3	Employer implements social arrangements according to the life insurance contract agreed upon between the employers and employees' unions	<i>Not specified</i>	<i>Not specified</i>	<i>Not specified</i>
KENYA Avocado CS11	<i>Not specified</i>	<i>Not specified</i>	<i>Not specified</i>	<u>Normal age:</u> 60 years <u>Earlier retirement:</u> 55 years, at the discretion of either the employee or the employer.

Overtimes, holiday working periods and nocturnal working periods

This table provides information on overtime and related remuneration.

TABLE 42 OVERTIMES AND EXTRA-PAY

SDGs – Indicator 8.8.2 & 1.1.1						
GRI - Disclosure 201-1						
COUNTRY	OVERTIME (Percentage of basic pay)	HOLIDAY WORKING HOURS	NOCTURNAL WORKING HOURS	OVERTIME IN HOLIDAY WORKING DAYS	NOCTURNAL WORKING HOURS IN HOLIDAY WORKING DAYS	BUSINNES TRIP
ALGERIA <i>Dairy CS13</i>	150%	The worker is entitled to compensatory rest of equal duration and shall benefit from the right to overtime pay.	The rules and conditions of night work are determined by collective agreements. The employer is not entitled to use female staff for night work	The worker is entitled to compensatory rest of equal duration and of equal duration and shall benefit from the right to overtime pay.	Worker entitled to compensatory rest of equal duration and of equal duration and shall benefit from the right to overtime pay. The employer is not entitled to use female staff for night work	Reimbursement of expenses is paid by the employer.
ARGENTINA <i>Dairy CS13</i> <i>Beef CS10</i>	150%	100%	reduce working hours	200%	200%	Depends on agreements between employer and employee
BRAZIL <i>Dairy CS13</i> <i>Beef CS10</i>	150%	100%	120%	200%	200%	<i>Not specified</i>
FRANCE <i>Dairy CS13</i> <i>Beef CS10</i>	125% (for the first 8 h) 150% (>8 h) Alternatively, the employee recovers hours with a 25% bonus	<i>Not specified</i>	<u>night worker:</u> at least twice a week, three hours of work per day from 21:00 to 06:00; 270 or more hours of work within 12 consecutive months between 21:00 and 6:00 --> increase of 20%; [Art 8.2]	<i>Not specified</i>	<i>Not specified</i>	Journey " work - work " included in working time= actual working time (paid) Higher than normal "work-to-work" journey outside working time= financial compensation (1/2 pay/h *travel time exceeding normal commuting time at home-to-work). Overnight transfer: the employer provides accommodation and catering. (distance allowance= 5 times

						the guaranteed minimum per night away). Personal vehicle: kilometre allowance.
GERMANY Dairy CS13 Beef CS10	<i>Not specified</i>	Employees working on Sundays: entitled to a replacement day of rest. Holiday work can be paid for or compensated by leave within 3 months. On the days preceding Christmas and New Year's Eve, regular working hours end at 12:00.	8 hours, maximum 10hours/day only if an average of 8h/night is not exceeded for an entire month.	There are no legal provisions governing the arrangements and the overtime bonus, which are governed by collective agreements and employment contracts. Overtime can be compensated with permits or wage supplements.	<i>Not specified</i>	<i>Not specified</i>
ITALY Dairy CS13 Beef CS10	+125%	+135%	+140%	+140%	+145%	governed by provincial contracts
MOROCCO Beef CS10	+125%	126%	+ 50% increase	126%	is equal to 26% of the remuneration for the 26 days of actual work immediately preceding the holiday for a fee.	Governed by contracts and agreement
NAMIBIA Beef CS10	150%	200%	106%	200%	200%	To be paid by the employer, specified in individual contracts
SOUTH AFRICA Dairy CS13 Beef CS10	150%	150%	between 18h-6h the work must be compensated by payment of an allowance or by a reduction of working hours and transport must be available. Compensated at least 10% of ordinary wage	<i>Not specified</i>	<i>Not specified</i>	<i>Not specified</i>
U.S.A. Dairy CS13 Beef CS10	150%	150%	The Act requires the inclusion in the regular rate of such extra premiums as nightshift differentials (whether they take the form of a percent of the base rate or an addition of so many cents per hour) (FLSA)	150%	The Act requires the inclusion in the regular rate of such extra premiums as nightshift differentials (whether they take the form of a percent of the base rate or an addition of so many cents per hour) (FLSA)	Travel that is all in a day's work, however, is considered hours worked and must be paid.
ZIMBABWE Dairy CS13	150%	250%	<i>Not specified</i>	200%	<i>Not specified</i>	<i>Not specified</i>
FINLAND Dairy CS3	+150% (for the first 2 h/d)	+200%	+120%	<i>Not specified</i>	<i>Not specified</i>	<i>Not specified</i>

	+200% for weekly overtime +150% (<8h) +200% (>8h)					
KENYA <i>Avocado CS11</i>	150%	200%	No premium payment for night work. The total working time, inclusive of overtime, may not exceed 144 hours for night workers.	200%	No premium payment for night work. Normal working hours at night cannot exceed 60 hours per week and overtime of 24 hours is allowed in a period of 2 consecutive weeks. The total working time, inclusive of overtime, may not exceed 144 hours for night workers.	Employers must pay

Payments

Information on remuneration and other benefits is set out in the table below. This indicator is of particular importance since it simultaneously satisfies both indicator 8.8.2, on working conditions and indicator 1.1, on poverty.

TABLE 43 PAYMENTS

SDGs indicator 1.1.1 SDGs indicator 8.8.2 GRI 201 disclosure 1					
COUNTRY	PAYMENT IN KIND	MINIMUM PAY	EXTRA-PAY	LONG SERVICE BONUS	SEVERANCE PAY
ALGERIA Dairy CS13	Not specified	0.80 euro/h 20,000 DZD/monthly	Not specified	Not specified	Paid per month for each year of work, max. 15 months.
ARGENTINA Dairy CS13 Beef CS10	max 20% of salary	0.19 euro/h 16.875 AR\$/month 95,88 AR\$/h	1 extra salary/year	Not specified	- <u>dismissal without just cause</u> : 1 month salary/each full year of service; - <u>employer dismisses an employee for a reason not attributable to the worker</u> : ¹ / ₂ -month salary for each full year of service; *Note: Payment limited by law for companies where collective agreements apply.
BRAZIL Dairy CS13 Beef CS10	Not specified	1.47 euro/h 1.320 R\$/month 246,44 euro/ month	2 extra salaries/year	Not specified	Not specified
FRANCE Dairy CS13 Beef CS10	Possible	10.15-20.70 euro/h *according to the level of specialization	Not specified	Every 6 years	¹ / ₄ of the monthly salary per year for the first 10 years of service; ¹ / ₃ monthly salary per year of service from the 11 th year.
GERMANY Dairy CS13 Beef CS10	Not specified	min 12 euro/h	Defined by collective agreements *Christmas, holiday and anniversary bonus	Not specified	- <u>Dismissal without just cause</u> : 50% of one month's wages for every year of service. - <u>Dismissal for just cause</u> : no severance pay
ITALY Dairy CS13 Beef CS10	Possible	5.60-8.24 euro/h *According to the level of specialization (monthly)	2 extra salaries/year	Every 2 years Amount: the salary is increased of 8.99-11.62 euro/month *According to the level of worker's specialization. Max 5 bonus	Sum of one year's salary for each year of service, all divided by 13.5
MOROCCO Beef CS10	Not considered for the calculation of the statutory minimum wage.	1.05 €euro/h 2.094 MAD/month	Not specified	2 years of service: +5% 5 years of service: +10% 12 years of service: +15% 20 years of service: 20% 25 years of service: +25%	<5 years of service: 96 hours' salary; 5-10 years of service: 144 hours' salary; 11-15 years of service: 192 hours' salary; >15 years of service: 240 hours' salary.
NAMIBIA Beef CS10	Max ¹ / ₃ of basic salary	0.07 euro/h 5.40 N\$/h	Not specified	Not specified	1 week's salary for every year of service.

SOUTH AFRICA Dairy CS13 Beef CS10	Max 10% of salary	1.16 euro/h 23.19 RAND/h	<i>Not specified</i>	<i>Not specified</i>	1 week's salary for every year of service.
U.S.A. Dairy CS13 Beef CS10	Possible	6.47 euro/h 7.25 \$/h	<i>Not specified</i>	<i>Not specified</i>	<i>Not specified</i>
ZIMBABWE Dairy CS13	Possible	0.87 euro/h 71.926 ZW\$/month	<i>Not specified</i>	<i>Not specified</i>	Employee with > 5 years of continuous service is entitled to a "bonus" equal to or greater than the amount obtained by multiplying the contractually agreed % of his current monthly salary at the time of termination by the number of years of continuous service. The bonus does not apply to an employee who is entitled to compensation from a private pension scheme.
FINLAND Dairy CS3	<i>Not specified</i>	9,20 euro/h	<i>Not specified</i>	On December 1st an extra pay for number of years served: 5-9y = 140e 10-15y = 190e 16-19y = 260e 20y or more = 345e	Severance period applied, if the period is not respected, full pay for those days will be reimbursed
KENYA Avocado CS11	Possible	117.50 euro/month 15120 KES/Month	<i>Not specified</i>	<i>Not specified</i>	<i>Not specified</i>

Working relationship

TABLE 44 WORKING RELATIONSHIP

SDG: Indicator 8.8.2			
GRI: Disclosure 402-1			
COUNTRY	PROBATIONARY PERIOD	FIRING	DISMISS
ALGERIA <i>Dairy CS13</i>	6-12 months	<i>Not specified</i>	Notice period under the conditions set out in the collective agreement.
ARGENTINA <i>Dairy CS13</i> <i>Beef CS10</i>	1-3 months	15-60 d notice to the employee Notice not needed if the employer pays an indemnity <i>(15 d' salary, plus 1- or 2-months' salary)</i>	15 d notice to the employer
BRAZIL <i>Dairy CS13</i> <i>Beef CS10</i>	1-3 months	30 d notice to the employee <u>Without a valid reason:</u> penalty.	30 d notice to the employer
FRANCE <i>Dairy CS13</i> <i>Beef CS10</i>	2-4 months	30-60 d month notice to employee, depends on the employment length	30 d notice to the employer
GERMANY <i>Dairy CS13</i> <i>Beef CS10</i>	1-6 months	15-180 d notice to employee, depends on the employment length	30 d notice to the employer
ITALY <i>Dairy CS13</i> <i>Beef CS10</i>	14, 20, 16 d (according to the level of specialization of the job)	60 d notice to employee	Just case: without notice Other cases: 30 d notice
MOROCCO <i>Beef CS10</i>	1.5-3 months	<i>Not specified</i>	Min 8 d notice to the employer
NAMIBIA <i>Beef CS10</i>	<i>Not specified</i>	7-30 d notice to employee, depends on the employment length	7-30 d notice, depends on the employment length
SOUTH AFRICA <i>Dairy CS13</i> <i>Beef CS10</i>	<i>Not specified</i>	7-30 d notice to employee, depends on the employment length	7-30 d notice, depends on the employment length
U.S.A. <i>Dairy CS13</i> <i>Beef CS10</i>	3-6 months	The <u>At Will</u> contract: employer has the right to fire employees at any time; <u>Just Cause:</u> notice needed	The <u>At Will</u> contract: employee has the right to leave at any time; <u>Just Cause:</u> notice needed.
ZIMBABWE <i>Dairy CS13</i>	3 months	3 months of notice	120 d notice to the employer
FINLAND <i>Dairy CS3</i>	1-6 months	Dismissal may be for just or required for economic reasons Dismissal periods for different lengths of employment	Depends on the employment length
KENYA <i>Avocado CS11</i>	2-12 months	30-90 d (Employee declared redundant: entitled to 21 d' pay/each completed year)	7-90 d notice, depends on the employment length

Forced and child labour

TABLE 45 CHILD LABOUR

	SDGs Indicator 8.7.1 SDGs Indicator 8.8.2
	GRI 408 disclosure 1 GRI 409 disclosure 1
COUNTRY	CHILD LABOUR
ALGERIA <i>Dairy CS13</i> <i>Beef CS10</i>	Min 19 years <u>Exception:</u> 16-19 years: with parents' consent; night shift forbidden
ARGENTINA <i>Dairy CS13</i> <i>Beef CS10</i>	Min 14 years <u>Exception:</u> <14 years: children can work with their family, but they can't perform dangerous tasks; 14-18 years: children can work autonomously with parents' consent
BRAZIL <i>Dairy CS13</i> <i>Beef CS10</i>	Min 16 years <u>Exception:</u> 14-16 years: apprenticeship
FRANCE <i>Dairy CS13</i> <i>Beef CS10</i>	Min 18 years <u>Exception:</u> 16 years: with parents' consent
GERMANY <i>Dairy CS13</i> <i>Beef CS10</i>	Min 17 years
ITALY <i>Dairy CS13</i> <i>Beef CS10</i>	Min 16 years
MOROCCO <i>Beef CS10</i>	Min 18 years <u>Exception:</u> 15-18 only with permission of the labour inspector
NAMIBIA <i>Beef CS10</i>	Min 14 years <u>Note:</u> 14-16 years cannot perform night work (8 pm - 7 am)
SOUTH AFRICA <i>Dairy CS13</i> <i>Beef CS10</i>	Min 15 years
U.S.A. <i>Dairy CS13</i> <i>Beef CS10</i>	Min 16 years <u>Exception:</u> -12-13 years: children can work with a parent -from 14 years: with training certificate or in apprenticeship, children can perform some hazardous occupations
ZIMBABWE <i>Dairy CS13</i>	Min 16 years
FINLAND <i>Dairy CS3</i>	Min 15 years
KENYA <i>Avocado CS11</i>	Authorisation by an officer needed. Denied if it forces the child to stay away from the family; where alcohol is sold; as a tour guide. Not considered forced: -military service -civilian duty -conviction in a court of law -in case of war or calamity -minor communal service

To conclude this section, a table summarising the main linkages between the reference SDGs and the GRI system is provided.

TABLE 46 SDGs TO GRI STANDARDS

SDGs	Sub goal	Indicator	GRI	Disclosure
	1.1 By 2030, eradicate extreme poverty for all people everywhere, currently measured as people living on less than \$1.25 a day	1.1.1 Proportion of the population living below the international poverty line by sex, age, employment status and geographical location (urban/rural)	201	Economic performance 1 - Direct economic value generated and distributed <i>Economic value distributed: operating costs, employee wages and benefits, payments to providers of capital, payments to government by country, and community investments;</i> 2 - Financial implications and other risks and opportunities due to climate change <i>Risks and opportunities posed by climate change that have the potential to generate substantive changes in operations, revenue, or expenditure</i> 3 - Defined benefit plan obligations and other retirement plans <i>If the plan's liabilities are met by the organization's general resources, the estimated value of those liabilities.</i> <i>If a separate fund exists to pay the plan's pension liabilities:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the extent to which the scheme's liabilities are estimated to be covered by the assets that have been set aside to meet them; - the basis on which that estimate has been arrived at; - when that estimate was made. <i>If a fund set up to pay the plan's pension liabilities is not fully covered, explain the strategy, if any, adopted by the employer to work towards full coverage, and the timescale, if any, by which the employer hopes to achieve full coverage.</i> <i>Percentage of salary contributed by employee or employer.</i> <i>Level of participation in retirement plans, such as participation in mandatory or voluntary schemes, regional, or country-based schemes, or those with financial impact.</i>
	1.3 Implement nationally appropriate social protection systems and measures for all, including floors, and by 2030 achieve substantial coverage of the poor and the vulnerable	1.3.1 Proportion of population covered by social protection floors/systems, by sex, distinguishing children, unemployed persons, older persons, persons with disabilities, pregnant women, newborns, work-injury victims and the poor and the vulnerable		
	2.3 By 2030, double the agricultural productivity and incomes of small-scale food producers, in particular women, indigenous peoples, family farmers, pastoralists and fishers, including through secure and equal access to land, other productive resources and inputs, knowledge, financial services, markets and opportunities for value addition and non-farm employment	2.3.2 Average income of small-scale food producers, by sex and indigenous status	201	Economic performance 1 - Direct economic value generated and distributed <i>Economic value distributed: operating costs, employee wages and benefits, payments to providers of capital, payments to government by country, and community investments;</i>
	5.1 End all forms of discrimination against all women and girls everywhere	5.1.1 Whether or not legal frameworks are in place to promote, enforce and	406	Non-discrimination 1 - Incidents of discrimination and corrective actions taken

				monitor equality and non-discrimination on the basis of sex			
	5.a	Undertake reforms to give women equal rights to economic resources, as well as access to ownership and control over land and other forms of property, financial services, inheritance and natural resources, in accordance with national laws	5.a.1	(a) Proportion of total agricultural population with ownership or secure rights over agricultural land, by sex; and (b) share of women among owners or rights-bearers of agricultural land, by type of tenure	409	Forced or Compulsory Labour	<p>1 - Operations and suppliers at significant risk for incidents of forced or compulsory labour <i>Operations and suppliers considered to have significant risk for incidents of forced or compulsory labour.</i> <i>Measures taken by the organization in the reporting period intended to contribute to the elimination of all forms of forced or compulsory labour.</i></p>
	8.3	Promote development-oriented policies that support productive activities, decent job creation, entrepreneurship, creativity and innovation, and encourage the formalization and growth of micro-, small- and medium-sized enterprises, including through access to financial services	8.3.1	Proportion of informal employment in total employment, by sector and sex	409	Forced or Compulsory Labour	<p>1 - Operations and suppliers at significant risk for incidents of forced or compulsory labour <i>Operations and suppliers considered to have significant risk for incidents of forced or compulsory labour.</i> <i>Measures taken by the organization in the reporting period intended to contribute to the elimination of all forms of forced or compulsory labour.</i></p>
					408	Child labour	<p>1 - Operations and suppliers at significant risk for incidents of child labor.</p>
	8.8	Protect labour rights and promote safe and secure working environments for all workers, including migrant workers, in particular women migrants, and those in precarious employment	8.8.2	Level of national compliance with labour rights (freedom of association and collective bargaining) based on International Labour Organization (ILO) textual sources and national legislation, by sex and migrant status	403	Occupational Health and Safety	<p>1 - Occupational health and safety management system <i>A statement of whether an occupational health and safety management system has been implemented.</i> <i>A description of the scope of workers, activities, and workplaces covered by the occupational health and safety management system, and an explanation of whether and, if so, why any workers, activities, or workplaces are not covered.</i></p> <p>2 - Hazard identification, risk assessment, and incident investigation <i>A description of the processes used to identify work-related hazards and assess risks on a routine and non-routine basis, and to apply the hierarchy of controls in order to eliminate hazards and minimize risks.</i> <i>A description of the policies and processes for workers to remove themselves from work situations that they believe could cause injury or ill health, and an explanation of how workers are protected against reprisals.</i></p> <p>3 - Occupational health services <i>A description of the occupational health services' functions that contribute to the identification and elimination of hazards and minimization of risks, and an explanation of how the organization ensures the quality of these services and facilitates workers' access to them</i></p> <p>4 - Worker participation, consultation, and communication on occupational health and safety <i>A description of the processes for worker participation and consultation in the development, implementation, and evaluation of the occupational health and safety management system, and for providing</i></p>

						<p><i>access to and communicating relevant information on occupational health and safety to workers.</i></p>
						<p>5 - Worker training on occupational health and safety <i>A description of any occupational health and safety training provided to workers, including generic training as well as training on specific work-related hazards, hazardous activities, or hazardous situations.</i></p>
						<p>6 - Promotion of worker health <i>An explanation of how the organization facilitates workers' access to non-occupational medical and healthcare services, and the scope of access provided.</i> <i>A description of any voluntary health promotion services and programs offered to workers to address major non-work-related health risks, including the specific health risks addressed, and how the organization facilitates workers' access to these services and programs.</i></p>
						<p>7 - Prevention and mitigation of occupational health and safety impacts directly linked by business relationships. <i>A description of the organization's approach to preventing or mitigating significant negative occupational health and safety impacts that are directly linked to its operations, products, or services by its business relationships, and the related hazards and risks.</i></p>
						<p>8 - Workers covered by an occupational health and safety management system <i>If the organization has implemented an occupational health and safety management system based on legal requirements and/or recognized standards/guidelines:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>the n° and % of all employees and workers who are not employees but whose work and/or workplace is controlled by the organization, who are covered by such a system;</i> - <i>the n° and % of all employees and workers who are not employees but whose work and/or workplace is controlled by the organization, who are covered by such a system that has been internally audited;</i> - <i>the n° and % of all employees and workers who are not employees but whose work and/or workplace is controlled by the organization, who are covered by such a system that has been audited or certified by an external party.</i> <p><i>Whether and, if so, why any workers have been excluded from this disclosure, including the types of workers excluded.</i> <i>Any contextual information necessary to understand how the data have been compiled, such as any standards, methodologies, and assumptions used.</i></p>
						<p>9 - Work-related injuries</p>
						<p>10 - Work-related ill health</p>
				407	Freedom of Association and Collective Bargaining	<p>1 - Operations and suppliers in which the right to freedom of association and collective bargaining may be at risk <i>Operations and suppliers in which workers' rights to exercise freedom of association or collective bargaining may be violated or at significant risk.</i></p>

Environmental sustainability

The in-depth study of environmental sustainability issues was carried out thanks to the participation in the activities of two organisations highly specialised in the sectors investigated by the case studies:

- [Agribenchmark beef](#) was involved in case study n.º 10: “Beef and policy coherence for sustainable development”.
- [IFCN](#) was involved in case study n.º13 “Dairy production, standards and competitiveness in global markets”.

The study carried out brought to light some information on the environmental impact of dairy production.

Dairy production, standards and competitiveness in global markets (CS #13)

For each country, the code number of typical farms is listed. The number of farms varies greatly depending on the country in question, and the environmental impact measured as kg CO₂/100 kg of milk produced is given for each of these typical farms. The proposed data refer to three consecutive years.

Germany

For Germany, a total of seven typical farms were analysed. It can be observed that for 70% of the farms, emissions undergo an upward trend over the three-year period, peaking in the second year and then increasing again.

TABLE 47 EMISSION IN GERMANY, DAIRY SECTOR (IFCN)

GERMANY									
Total CO ₂ emissions for milk			DE-30S	DE-80S	DE-109S	DE-155N	DE-314N	DE-700E	DE-1200E
	2020	kg CO ₂ /100 kg milk	110.7	105.7	106.2	135.5	117.8	107.0	103.8
	2021	kg CO ₂ /100 kg milk	112.4	100.9	103.8	129.8	115.5	103.7	100.9
	2022	kg CO ₂ /100 kg milk	133.7	137.0	144.2	145.0	133.3	103.6	99.8

FIGURE 21 EMISSION IN GERMANY, DAIRY SECTOR

France

For France, a total of three typical farms were analysed. An increase in emissions can be observed in the last year.

TABLE 48 EMISSION IN FRANCE, DAIRY SECTOR (IFCN)

FRANCE					
			FR-40MC	FR-100C	FR-66W
Total CO ₂ emissions for milk	2020	kg CO ₂ /100 kg milk	141.3	111.8	102.5
	2021	kg CO ₂ /100 kg milk	130.4	96.7	103.3
	2022	kg CO ₂ /100 kg milk	147.1	124.7	131.0

FIGURE 22 EMISSION IN FRANCE, DAIRY SECTOR

Italy

For Italy, a total of two typical farms were analysed. Emissions remain stable in the first two years, while they increase significantly in 2022.

TABLE 49 EMISSION IN ITALY, DAIRY SECTOR (IFCN)

ITALY				
Total CO ₂ emissions for milk			IT-154	IT-229
	2020	kg CO ₂ /100 kg milk	105.2	106.7
	2021	kg CO ₂ /100 kg milk	106.5	107.6
	2022	kg CO ₂ /100 kg milk	143.0	142.1

FIGURE 23 EMISSION IN ITALY, DAIRY SECTOR

Algeria

For Algeria, a total of two typical farms were analysed. Emissions remain stable in the first two years, while they increase significantly in 2022.

TABLE 50 EMISSION IN ALGERIA, DAIRY SECTOR (IFCN)

ALGERIA				
Total CO ₂ emissions for milk			DZ-6	DZ-18
	2020	kg CO ₂ /100 kg milk	212.1	174.7
	2021	kg CO ₂ /100 kg milk	209.4	170.9
	2022	kg CO ₂ /100 kg milk	239.9	200.6

FIGURE 24 EMISSION IN ALGERIA, DAIRY SECTOR

Zimbabwe

For Zimbabwe, a total of two typical farms were analysed. The two typical farms represent two opposite trends: in the first case, emissions have decreasing levels of emissions. In the second case there is a gradual and constant increase.

TABLE 51 EMISSION IN ZIMBABWE, DAIRY SECTOR

ZIMBABWE				
			ZW-110	ZW-460
Total CO ₂ emissions for milk	2020	kg CO ₂ /100 kg milk	188.4	117.7
	2021	kg CO ₂ /100 kg milk	180.8	146.0
	2022	kg CO ₂ /100 kg milk	156.0	181.2

FIGURE 25 EMISSION IN ZIMBABWE, DAIRY SECTOR

South Africa

Again, the values are discordant and report three very different scenarios. In one case, emissions in the three-year period remain constant, in the second case there is a decrease in kg of CO₂ produced in the third year, and in the last scenario there is a significant increase in 2022.

TABLE 52 EMISSION IN SOUTH AFRICA, DAIRY SECTOR

SOUTH AFRICA					
			ZA-230	ZA-650	ZA-800
Total CO ₂ emissions for milk	2020	kg CO ₂ /100 kg milk	169.8	170.1	110.3
	2021	kg CO ₂ /100 kg milk	167.8	173.1	109.6
	2022	kg CO ₂ /100 kg milk	173.5	150.8	138.2

FIGURE 26 EMISSION IN SOUTH AFRICA, DAIRY SECTOR

United States of America

For the United States of America, 10 different typical companies were considered, all of which confirm constant emissions in the period 2020-2021 and a significant increase in the third year.

TABLE 53 EMISSION IN U.S.A., DAIRY SECTOR

United States of America											
Total CO ₂ emissions for milk kg CO ₂ /100 kg milk		US-80WI	US-500WI	US-65NY	US-450NY	US-2350NY	US-1200ID	US-2600ID	US-1100CA	US-3000CA	US-2272NM
2020		117.8	142.5	127.3	119.2	110.3	123.5	106.6	100.5	97.8	99.3
2021		111.5	127.7	119.7	112.3	111.3	123.2	109.8	99.4	98.6	101.0
2022		142.1	168.6	163.4	149.6	151.5	143.3	127.7	121.0	119.1	120.5

FIGURE 27 EMISSION IN U.S.A., DAIRY SECTOR

Argentina

For Argentina, a total of seven typical farms were analysed. Farms confirm an increase in emissions in the third year after a decrease in 2021.

TABLE 54 EMISSION IN ARGENTINA, DAIRY SECTOR (IFCN)

Argentina						
			AR-180	AR-400	AR-280	AR-600
Total CO ₂ emissions for milk	2020	kg CO ₂ /100 kg milk	122.7	110.1	109.8	118.6
	2021	kg CO ₂ /100 kg milk	111.3	96.9	98.3	106.9
	2022	kg CO ₂ /100 kg milk	139.2	129.6	124.4	143.7

FIGURE 28 EMISSION IN ARGENTINA, DAIRY SECTOR

Brazil

All typical farms confirm a significant increase in emissions during the third year.

TABLE 55 EMISSION IN BRAZIL, DAIRY SECTOR (IFCN)

BRAZIL									
Total CO ₂ emissions for milk			BR-34S	BR-111S	BR-350S	BR-56S	BR-180SE	BR-320SE	BR-64S
	2020	kg CO ₂ /100 kg milk	89.3	83.7	73.9	89.8	128.2	121.9	107.6
	2021	kg CO ₂ /100 kg milk	84.3	78.8	69.2	86.9	129.8	121.7	99.1
	2022	kg CO ₂ /100 kg milk	110.9	101.8	93.8	113.9	149.5	142.6	121.2

FIGURE 29 EMISSION IN BRAZIL, DAIRY SECTOR (IFCN)

GHG Emission of beef production (CS #10)

Global overview of dynamics

To draw a global overview of the emissions linked to agri-food system and -in particular- to beef, reference is done to the FAO report, *Tackling climate change through livestock: A global assessment of emissions and mitigation opportunities* (FAO, 2013), which still represents one of the most comprehensive estimates of livestock's contribution to global warming (as well as the sector's potential to help tackle the problem). To complete and to update the framework reference is also done to other and more recent FAO/FAOSTAT reports (FAO, 2016; FAO 2019; FAOSTAT 2000-2020): the patterns of GHG emissions (e.g., Proportions among species/commodities as for the global impact) have not changed, while the absolute values of GHG emissions can have slightly changed. This can be explained partially to a slight change in emissions and partially to a constant finetuning of assessment/estimate tools.

The **livestock sector** plays an important role in climate change, with GHG emissions along livestock supply chains estimated at **7.1 gigatonnes CO₂-eq per annum, representing 14.5% of all human-induced emissions.**

Cattle (beef and milk) are the main contributor to the agri-food sector's emissions with about 4.6 gigatonnes CO₂-eq, **representing 65% of sector emissions.** Beef cattle (producing meat and non-edible outputs) and dairy cattle (producing both meat and milk, in addition to non-edible outputs) generate similar amounts of GHG emissions (beef slightly more). Pigs, poultry, buffaloes and small ruminants have much lower emission levels, with each representing between 7 and 10% of sector emissions (Figure 30).

FIGURE 30 GLOBAL ESTIMATES OF EMISSIONS BY SPECIES* (FAO, 2013) - GHG EMISSION VALUES ARE COMPUTED IN GLEAM

*Includes emissions attributed to edible products and to other goods and services, such as draught power and wool

1 Producing meat and non-edible outputs

2 Producing milk and meat as well as non-edible outputs

Source: [GLEAM](#)

Beef is the commodity with highest total emissions and emission intensities: it contributes 2.9 gigatonnes CO₂-eq, or 41%, and cattle milk 1.4 gigatonnes CO₂-eq, or 20%, of total sector emissions. They are followed by pig meat, with 0.7 gigatonnes CO₂-eq, or 9% of emissions, buffalo milk and meat (8%), chicken meat and eggs (8%), and small ruminant milk and meat (6%). The rest are emissions from other poultry species and non-edible products.

Figure 31 describes this pattern of proportions in a visual way.

FIGURE 31 TOTAL EMISSIONS BY COMMODITY

Source: GLEAM 2 – FAO, 2019

When emissions are expressed on a *per protein basis*, beef is the commodity with the highest emission intensity (amount of GHGs emitted per unit of output produced), with an average of over 300 kg CO₂-eq per kg of protein; followed by meat and milk from small ruminants, with averages of 165 and 112 kg CO₂-eq per kg of protein, respectively. Cow milk, chicken products and pork have lower global average emission intensities, all below 100 kg CO₂-eq per kg of edible protein (Figure 32).

FIGURE 32 GLOBAL EMISSION INTENSITY BY COMMODITY (FAO, 2013) - GHG EMISSION VALUES ARE COMPUTED IN GLEM

Source: [GLEM](#)

Figure 31 **Error! Reference source not found.** describes this pattern in a visual way: as above anticipated, absolute values in Figure 31 **Error! Reference source not found.** (FAO, 2019) slightly differ from values in Figure 32 **Error! Reference source not found.** (FAO, 2013) because they changed during the years, partially due to concrete evolution of the emissions and partially to an evolution of estimate tools. Conversely, patterns are constant.

FIGURE 33 EMISSION INTENSITY PER SPECIES (EXPRESSED IN CO₂-EQ.) BY COMMODITY

Source: [GLEM 2](#) – FAO, 2019

Figure 32 and Figure 33 also display the variability of the intensity of emissions which is particularly high in beef. This variability depends on the different level of efficiency of production systems in different areas of the world.

From a geographical perspective, regional emissions and production profiles vary widely (Figure 34). Differences are explained by the respective shares of ruminants (higher emissions) or monogastric in total livestock production, and by differences in emission intensities for each product and production system (efficiency), between regions. In **Error! Reference source not found.**, focus can be done on beef (dark blue portions).

Latin America and the Caribbean (LAC) have the highest level of emissions (almost 1.3 gigatonnes CO₂-eq), driven by an important production of specialized beef. Although at reduced pace in recent years, ongoing land-use change contributes to high CO₂ emissions in the region, due to the expansion

of both pasture and cropland for feed production (one third of all the emissions. Another third is linked to enteric CH₄ emissions (Figure 34).

With the highest livestock production and relatively high emission intensities for its beef and pork, East Asia has the second highest level of emissions (more than 1 gigatonnes CO₂-eq).

North America and Western Europe have similar GHG emission totals (over 0.6 gigatonnes CO₂-eq) and also fairly similar levels of protein output. However, emission patterns are different. In North America, almost two-thirds of emissions originate from beef production which has high emission intensities. In contrast, beef in Western Europe mainly comes from dairy herds with much lower emission intensities. In North America, emission intensities for chicken, pork and milk are lower than in Western Europe because the region generally relies on feed with lower emission intensity.

South Asia's total sector emissions are at the same level as North America and Western Europe, but its protein production is half what is produced in those areas. Ruminants contribute a large share due to their high emission intensity. For the same reason, emissions in sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) are large, despite a low protein output.

FIGURE 34 LIVESTOCK GHG EMISSIONS AND LIVESTOCK PRODUCTION, BY COMMODITY AND REGIONS (FAO, 2013)

LAC= Latin America and Caribbean; SSA= Sub-Saharan Africa; NENA= Near East and North Africa region
Source: GLEAM

Focusing to beef, Figure 35 shows the proportion of different sources of GHG emissions with reference to intensity (emissions per kilogram of carcass weight - kg CO₂-eq.kg CW⁻¹) in different regions. Reference is also done to regional beef production (·).

Across regions, enteric emissions of CH₄ represents from one third to a half of emissions intensity. NO₂ deriving from manure management/application varies from one sixth to one third (Latin America and the Caribbean, sub-Saharan Africa).

Emission intensities for beef are highest in South Asia, sub-Saharan Africa, Latin America and the Caribbean, and East and Southeast Asia. Higher emissions are largely caused by low feed digestibility (leading to higher enteric and manure emissions), poorer animal husbandry and lower slaughter weights (slow growth rates leading to more emissions per kg of meat produced) and higher age at slaughter (longer life leading to more emissions). In Latin America and the Caribbean, one-third of the emissions (24 kg CO₂-eq/kg carcass weight) from beef production is estimated to come from pasture expansion into forested areas. This estimate is to be taken with caution, given the

numerous methodological and data uncertainties affecting land-use change emissions estimates (FAO, 2013). In Europe, about 80% of the beef is produced from dairy animals (surplus calves and culled cows), resulting in lower emission intensities.

Anyway, when considering the global GHG emissions as a whole, this proportion (CO₂ from pasture expansion/GHG emissions) drops to one sixth, confirming that pasture expansion is a critical source of emissions in specific regions.

FIGURE 35 REGIONAL VARIATION IN BEEF PRODUCTION AND GHG EMISSIONS INTENSITIES (FAO, 2013)

CW: carcass weight
Source: GLEAM

FIGURE 36 GLOBAL EMISSIONS FROM BEEF SUPPLY CHAIN, BY CATEGORY OF EMISSIONS (FAO, 2013)

TABLE 56 GLOBAL PRODUCTION, EMISSIONS AND EMISSION INTENSITY FOR CATTLE MILK AND BEEF (FAO, 2013)

Herd	System	Production (Million tonnes)		Emissions (Million tonnes CO ₂ -eq)		Emission intensity (kg CO ₂ -eq/kg product)	
		Milk ¹	Meat ²	Milk	Meat	Milk ¹	Meat ²
Dairy	Grazing	77.6	4.8	227.2	104.3	2.9 ³	21.9 ³
	Mixed	430.9	22.0	1 104.3	381.9	2.6 ³	17.4 ³
	Total dairy	508.6	26.8	1 331.1	486.2	2.6³	18.2³
Specialized beef	Grazing		8.6		875.4		102.2 ³
	Mixed		26.0		1 462.8		56.2 ³
	Total beef		34.6		2 338.4		67.6³
Post-harvest emissions ⁴				87.6	12.4		
Totals		508.6	61.4	1 419.1	2 836.8	2.8⁵	46.2⁵

Note:

Grassland-based (or grazing) systems: Livestock production systems in which more than 10% of the dry matter fed to animals is farm-produced and in which annual average stocking rates are less than ten livestock units per ha of agricultural land

Mixed systems: Livestock production systems in which more than 10% of the dry matter fed to livestock comes from crop by-products and/or stubble or more than 10% of the value of production comes from non-livestock farming activities

1 Product: FPCM

2 Product: carcass weight (CW)

3 Does not include post-harvest emissions

4 Computed at commodity and country level

5 Includes post-harvest emissions

An interesting comparison to focus on is the milk vs beef commodity (Table 56), most of all in terms of emission intensity (kg CO₂-eq/kg milk or meat). In fact, emission intensity of 1 kg of meat coming from dairy beef is 18.2 kg CO₂-eq (blue frame) while emission intensity of 1 kg of meat coming from specialized beef is 67.6 kg CO₂-eq (red frame). This apparently peculiar difference among those two types of production is actually intrinsic: emissions coming from meat from dairy cattle are shared by emissions coming from milk produced by the same cattle. The next figure shows the contribution of dairy sector to beef production. Moreover, meat coming from dairy cattle in Countries specialized for dairy production mostly derives from animals which are slaughtered at 4-6 months of age and reared in barns, while cattle specialized for beef production have a longer life cycle (up to 24 months) and they are often reared in pasture and therefore they have a less efficient Feed Conversion Rate.

FIGURE 37 CONCEPTUAL MODEL OF LARGE RUMINANT DAIRY AND BEEF PRODUCTION SYSTEMS SHOWING THE DIFFERENT LIFE STAGES, RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN THE SYSTEMS AND OUTPUTS

FAO. 2016. *Environmental performance of large ruminant supply chains: Guidelines for assessment*. Livestock Environmental Assessment and Performance Partnership. FAO, Rome, Italy.

An incisive overview at global level of flow emissions in cattle supply chain is provided by Figure 38. Some general mechanisms are clearly displayed.

With a perspective focused on production activities, the total emissions of the cattle supply chain (4.6 gigatonnes) derive for 54% from livestock production (2.5 gigatonnes), for nearly 44% from feed production (2.0 gigatonnes) and the remaining quota (2%) derive from post-farm transport and processing (0.1 gigatonnes). This shows “where” theoretically operate (in terms of step of productive chain) when trying to mitigate GHG emissions. It must be notes that these “environmental” lever points could not correspond to “social” lever points, able to impact effectively on human welfare. In fact, post-farm transport and processing activities, even if affecting only marginally GHG emissions, are crucial in a welfare perspective.

Focusing on products, beef from specialized herd impacts for 2.4 on 4.6 gigatonnes (52%), while beef from dairy herd impacts for 0.5 gigatonnes (11%) and milk impacts for 30% and draft/manure used as fuel 7%. The difference between the impact of beef from specialized herd and beef from dairy herd can be explained one again with the fact that the emissions of the latter is shared with milk production, mitigating the final effect.

FIGURE 38 GLOBAL FLOW EMISSIONS IN CATTLE SUPPLY CHAIN, BY PRODUCTION ACTIVITIES AND PRODUCTS (FAO, 2013)

*Embedded energy related to the manufacture of on-farm buildings and equipment is

included in this category.

Source: GLEAM.

Global overview of trends

Considering the total anthropogenic GHG emissions, the agri-food systems as a whole account for one-third. Those agri-food emissions are generated within the farm gate, from crop and livestock production activities, by land-use change, for instance deforestation and peatland drainage to make room for agriculture and in pre- and post-production processes, such as food manufacturing, retail, household consumption and food disposal (FAOSTAT 2000-2020).

Globally, the farm gate in 2020 represented nearly half of total agri-food systems emissions, pre- and post-production processes contributed one-third and land-use change one-fifth (FAOSTAT 2000-2020).

In 2020, global annual anthropogenic GHG emissions reached 52 Gt CO₂-eq, down 4% from 54 Gt CO₂-eq in 2019 – reflecting a well-documented reduction in economic activities due to the COVID-19 pandemic. They were nonetheless 34% higher than in 2000. At the same time, emissions from agri-food systems were 16 Gt CO₂-eq in 2020, down 3% from 2019, but 9% higher than in 2000.

The share of agri-food systems in total emissions in 2020 (31%) confirmed the downward trend from the levels of 2000 (38%), a consequence of agri-food systems emissions growing significantly more slowly than the rest of the economy, dominated by fossil fuels combustion for energy use. In fact, non-food emissions grew nearly 50% since 2000. Agri-food systems emissions per capita likewise decreased over the period, from 2.4 t CO₂eq/cap to 2.0 t CO₂eq/cap (FAOSTAT 2000-2020).

FIGURE 39 GLOBAL AGRI-FOOD SYSTEM EMISSIONS BY COMPONENT AND INDICATOR

FAO. 2022. Emissions totals. In: *FAO*. Rome. Cited October 2022. <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/GT> and
 FAO. 2022. Emissions shares. In: *FAO*. Rome. Cited October 2022. <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/EM>

In 2020, Africa had the largest share of agri-food systems in total emissions (59%), consistently with the predominance of agriculture in most economies of the region. The shares were much lower in the Americas (40%), Oceania (38%) and Europe (32%) and lowest in Asia (23%), reflecting the economic

efficiency of more intensive mixed and modern production systems (**Error! Reference source not found.**).

The relative role of the three components in total emissions from agri-food systems varies across regions, reflecting structural differences in production and distribution systems around the world (Figure 40). Emissions in Africa and the Americas had significant land-use change components (1.2–1.3 Gt CO₂eq), respectively 44% and 31% of the total agri-food systems emissions, reflecting the extensive nature of agriculture in both regions and its impact on surrounding ecosystems. Conversely, significant pre- and post- production emissions were observed in Asia (43%, or 2.9 Gt CO₂eq) and especially in Europe (53% or 1.0 Gt CO₂eq), where this component was in fact the largest contributor. Emissions produced within the farm gate remained the dominant component of agri-food systems emissions in Oceania (71%), Asia (50%) and the Americas (42%).

FIGURE 40 REGIONAL AGRI-FOOD SYSTEMS EMISSIONS AND SHARE IN TOTAL EMISSIONS IN 2020 (FAOSTAT, 2000-2020)

FAO. 2022. Emissions totals. In: *FAO*. Rome. Cited October 2022. <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/GT> and
 FAO. 2022. Emissions shares. In: *FAO*. Rome. Cited October 2022. <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/EM>

The variation of farm-gate emission intensity from 2000 to 2020 is displayed in the next figure. In 2020, farm-gate emissions by kg of beef were 32 kg CO₂eq/kg, a high value that is largely due to methane production by ruminant fermentation. Indeed, the emissions intensities of monogastric animals were much smaller: nearly 2 kg CO₂eq/kg for pork and less than 1 kg CO₂eq/kg for chicken. The global emissions intensity of cow milk was 1 kg CO₂eq per kg of

milk. The global emissions intensities of cereals were 1 kg CO₂eq/kg for rice and 0.2 kg CO₂eq/kg for other cereals. The GHG intensity of hen eggs was 0.6 kg CO₂eq/kg.

Farm-gate emissions intensities had a marked long-term declining trend since 2000 across all commodities, with the largest reduction computed for cow milk (-24%) and rice (-14%) (Figure 41). Such reductions reflect increases in crop and livestock production efficiency over time, often achieved through economies of scale.

FIGURE 41 GLOBAL EMISSIONS INTENSITIES (2000-2020) AND % CHANGE

FAO. 2022. Emissions intensities. In: FAO. Rome. Cited October 2022 <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/EI>

Focusing on beef production, the following figure **Error! Reference source not found.** shows the trend of emissions intensity in different regions from 2000 to 2020.

The 2020 emissions intensity of beef was highest in Africa (66 kg CO₂eq/kg), followed by the Americas and Asia (29 kg CO₂eq/kg in both regions), Oceania (21 kg CO₂eq/kg) and Europe (17 kg CO₂eq/kg).

Between 2000 and 2020, most regions exhibited a downward trend in the emissions intensity of beef. The largest reductions were found in Asia and Oceania (-37% and -27%, respectively) whereas Europe and the Americas

showed smaller reductions in the 3–5% range. Africa was the only region with an increase (6%).

FIGURE 42 EMISSIONS INTENSITY OF BEEF BY REGION, FROM 2000 TO 2020

FAO. 2022. Emissions intensities. In: *FAO*. Rome. Cited October 2022. <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/EI>

Geographical focus¹³

In the following paragraphs the emissions related to beef production in nine countries will be considered.

Focus Countries are:

- Germany
- France
- Italy
- USA
- Brazil
- Argentina
- Morocco
- South Africa
- Namibia

In the Annex 1, it is possible to find several tables that grouped all the data, according to the reference.

In the comment related to each Country/Region the lowest and the higher values reported in references are pointed out. On some occasions, it has been necessary to express different values, according to different measurement units, which are one of the critical issues of emissions (e.g., kg CO₂-eq/kg of meat, kg CO₂-eq/kg of live weight, kg CO₂-eq/kg of protein).

For certain countries data are not easily available.

¹³ Before proceeding to the reading of the geographical detail, please find below a short legend that may be useful for a better understanding.

Legenda:

- BFM: Bone Free Meat
- System Boundary: segment of the production process (start and finish) that is considered in a certain study. E.g., From cradle to farm gate.
- Allocation: distribution of GHG emissions to different products occurring in multi-outputs productions
- LW: Live Weight

Germany

In Germany, according to authors and to reference years, the emissions of beef sector vary from 13.6 kg CO₂-eq/kg of meat (Reinhardt G et al., 2020) to 26.9 kg CO₂-eq/kg of bone free meat (Mieleitner J et al., 2012).

TABLE 57 CO₂ FOOTPRINTS OF SELECTED MEAT AND MEAT SUBSTITUTE PRODUCTS, IN 2019, "AT THE SUPERMARKET CHECKOUT" IN GERMANY IN KG OF CO₂-EQ PER KG OF FOOD¹⁴.

No.	Foodstuff	CO ₂ footprint [kg CO ₂ eq / kg food]
1	Beef, average ³	13.6
2	Beef (organic) ³	21.7
3	Beef patty, frozen	9.0
4	Minced beef ⁴	9.2
5	Minced beef (organic) ⁴	15.1
6	Chicken, average	5.5
7	Chicken, frozen	5.7
8	Chicken, nuggets	3.3
9	Chicken, sausage slices	2.9
10	Fish, aquaculture	5.1
11	Fish, wild-catch, bulk good, frozen	2.4
12	Fish, wild-catch, fresh	4.0
13	Fish, wild-catch, speciality, frozen	10.0
14	Game meat, deer ⁵	11.5
15	Lupine flour	0.4

Source: (Reinhardt G. et Al., 2020)

France

In France, according to authors and to reference years, the emissions of beef sector vary from 17.4 kg CO₂-eq/kg of meat (Dollé J et al., 2012) to 40.0 kg CO₂-eq/kg of bone free meat (Nguyen TTH at al., 2012).

Parallely, Veysset et al. (2010) focusing on the region of Charlerois report footprint as kg CO₂e per kg Live Weight, indicating the range 14.3-18.3.

¹⁴ ³ Both conventional beef (11 to >30 kg CO₂-eq / kg food) and organic beef (16 to >30 kg CO₂-eq / kg food) show wide ranges, with organic beef tending to perform slightly worse.

⁴ Processed meat such as minced meat has lower CO₂ footprint than fine meat; the range is also smaller: 7 to 26 CO₂-eq / kg food for conventional beef mince.

Italy

In Italy, according to authors and to reference years, the emissions of beef sector vary from 15.3 kg CO₂-eq/kg of bone free meat (Benatti L et al., 2012) to 27.3 kg CO₂-eq/kg of bone free meat (Lesschen JP et al., 2011).

For organic production, Vitali A et al. (2018) reports 24.47 CO₂-eq/kg meat.

Finally, to explore another unit of measurement (kg CO₂eq/kg of protein), Zucali et al., 2017 reports the emission value of some productions in Lombardy region. In particular, beef from specialized systems has an emission of 80 kg CO₂-eq/kg of protein while beef from dairy production reaches 85 kg CO₂-eq/kg of protein (Sandrucci A, Trevisi E, 2022. Produzioni Animali, EdiSES Università).

United States of America

In USA, according to authors, to reference years and to system boundaries, the emissions of beef sector vary from 22.30 to 41.73 CO₂eq/kg meat (Gerber PJ et al., 2013).

Focusing on the Upper Midwest, Pelletier et al. (2010) report that feed lot finished beef emissions are 19.2 kg CO₂-eq/kg Live Weight, while pasture finished beef emissions are 14.8 kg CO₂-eq/kg Live Weight.

Latin America and Caribbean

The beef sector of Latin America and Caribbean considered as a whole, according to Gerber PJ et al. (2013) produces from 49 to 69 CO₂-eq/kg meat (Gerber PJ et al., 2013).

Some data referring to single Countries are also available.

Argentina

In Argentina, according to authors and to reference years, the emissions of beef sector vary from 22 (González AD et al., 2011) to 35 CO₂-eq/kg meat (Benatti L et al., 2015).

Brazil

In Brazil, according to authors, to reference years, to system boundaries and to farming efficiency, the emissions of beef sector vary from 9.2 (Dick, M et al., 2014) to 64 CO₂-eq/kg meat (Mieleitner J et al., 2012).

Considering the emissions kg of Live Weight, the value goes from 14 to 22 CO₂-eq/kg live weight (Cederberg C et al, 2011).

Sub-Saharan Africa

The beef sector of sub-Saharan Africa considered as a whole, according to Gerber PJ et al. (2013) produces 100.72 CO₂-eq/kg meat.

South Africa

For this Country no data are available as for total emissions by beef sector, expressed as CO₂-eq per kg of meat or protein or live weight.

Du Toit et al. (2013) reports CH₄ emissions which are the larger contribution to GHG emission in ruminant (and beef) sector. The authors consider separately commercial feed cattle and communal beef cattle. Using for example the animal class of “bulls” as a point of comparison, the Methane Emission Factor of the commercial sector is 113 CH₄ kg/head per year, while in the communal sector the Methane Emission Factor of bulls is 84 CH₄ kg/head per year.

TABLE 58 METHANE EMISSION FACTORS FOR COMMERCIAL BEEF CATTLE

Animal class	Weight (kg)	MEF _{entic} (kg/h/year)	MEF _{manure} (kg/h/year)
Bulls	733	113	0.022
Cows	475	92.6	0.018
Heifers	365	75.9	0.016
Oxen	430	89.4	0.018
Young oxen	193	51.6	0.012
Calves	190	51.6	0.012

MEF: methane emissions factor; kg/h/year: kg/head/year.

TABLE 59 METHANE EMISSION FACTORS FOR COMMUNAL BEEF CATTLE

Animal class	Weight (kg)	MEF _{entic} (kg/h/year)	MEF _{manure} (kg/h/year)
Bulls	462	83.8	0.017
Cows	360	73.1	0.015
Heifers	292	62.5	0.013
Oxen	344	72.6	0.015
Young oxen	154	41.6	0.010
Calves	152	40.9	0.010

The main represented commercial cattle category in South African is dairy cattle (almost 3,000,000 heads). A smaller quota is represented by beef reared in feedlots (almost 600,000 heads). The enteric fermentation emission factor of this latter category is 59 kg CH₄ per head per year, considering 2010-2017 (National GHG Inventory Report South Africa, 2017).

Namibia

For this Country no data are available as for total emissions by beef sector, expressed as CO₂-eq per kg of meat or protein or live weight.

In the National GHG Inventory Report 2000-2012 (NIR 2) aggregated emission estimates from enteric fermentation (EF) and manure management (MM) from year 2000 to 2012 are presented and expressed in Gigagrams CO₂-eq: the value goes from 4164 (EF) and 350 (MM) in 2000 to 5170 (EF) and 508 (MM) in 2012. The trend shows a certain slight fluctuation until 2010 while in 2011 1st 2012 a clear increase is displayed.

CH₄ emissions largely represent the main contribution to GHG coming from livestock. In 2012, out of 265 million kg CO₂-eq coming from CH₄ produced in Agriculture, Forestry and Other Land Use, 254.2 million kg CO₂-eq came from Livestock. Out of these, 220 million kg CO₂-eq came from enteric fermentation of cattle and 8.8 million kg CO₂-eq came from manure management of cattle.

North Africa

The beef sector of North Africa considered as a whole, according to Gerber PJ et al. (2013) produces 40 CO₂-eq/kg meat.

Morocco

The Climate Chance Observatory team, in "*Moroccan society's uneven response to the proliferation of waste*" (Climate Chance - global observatory on non-state climate action, 2016) reports that in Morocco, in 2012, GHG emissions related to agriculture were 21.3% of total emissions, citing as source *World Bank* (2017), based on data from the Ministry of the Environment (2016).

The same authors report Morocco's GHG emissions in kilotons CO₂-eq (source: UNFCCC), which go from 40,000 (in 1994) to 100,000 (in 2012), just to have a figure of the order of magnitude.

A previous document (*First National Communication United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change, 2001*), reporting data from 1994, identified as 25% the contribution of agriculture to total Morocco emissions, with a value of 12,000 kilotons CO₂-eq.

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6. Capper J.L. (2011). The environmental impact of beef production in the United States: 1977 compared with 2007. *Journal of Animal Science*, 89: 4249–61. doi:10.2527/jas.2010-3784
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Annex 1

Germany

Clune et al., 2017

Reference	Year of study	Report type	kg CO ₂ -eq/kg produce, BFM after conversion	Notes <i>(conventional farming assumed unless stated):</i>
Lesschen, J. P., M. van den Berg, H. J. Westhoek, H. P. Witzke and O. Oenema (2011). <i>Greenhouse gas emission profiles of European livestock sectors</i> . <i>Animal Feed Science and Technology</i> 166–167(0): 16-28.	2011	Journal	24.30	MITERRA-Europe model
Mieleitner, J., M. Alig, F. Grandl, T. Nemecek and G. r. Gaillard (2012). Environmental impact of beef – role of slaughtering, meat processing and transport. 8th International Conference on Life Cycle Assessment in the Agri-Food Sector (LCA Food 2012). Saint Malo, France. Rennes.	2012	Conference	26.93	-

Reference	Classification	System Boundaries	Functional Unit (FU)	GhG Emissions (kg CO ₂ e / FU)	Allocation
Zehetmeier, M., Baudracco, J., Hoffmann, H. & Heißenhuber, A. 2012. Does increasing milk yield per cow reduce greenhouse gas emissions? A system approach <i>Animal</i> , 6: 154–66. doi:10.1017/S1751731111001467	Comparison dairy + beef combined system	cradle to farm gate but it is a bovine system including milk and beef system	kg meat	Milk: 0.98 – 1.35; Beef: 5.6 – 14.6 Milk: 0.89 – 1.06; Beef: 10.8 – 16.2	None: GHG emissions are allocated all to milk Economic: GHG emissions occurring during dairy cow production and heifer rearing are allocated to milk according to their economic value

France

<i>Clune et al., 2017</i>				
Reference	Year of study	Report type	kg CO ₂ -eq/kg produce, BFM after conversion	Notes (conventional farming assumed unless stated):
Dollé J. B., A. Gac, V. Manneville, S. Moreau and E. Lorinquer (2012). Life cycle assessment on dairy and beef cattle farms in France. 8 th International Conference on Life Cycle Assessment in the Agri-Food Sector (LCA Food 2012). Saint Malo, France. Rennes.	2012	Conference	17.35	
Salou T., Espagnol S., Gac A., Ponchant P., Tocqueville A. I., Colomb V. and H. M. G. v. d. Werf (2014). <i>Life Cycle Assessment of French livestock products: Results of the AGRIBALYSE® program</i> . Proceedings of the 9th International Conference on Life Cycle Assessment in the Agri-Food Sector. San Francisco: 1154-1162.	2014	Conference	20.20	mean AGRIBALYSE®
Salou T., Espagnol S., Gac A., Ponchant P., Tocqueville A. I., Colomb V. and H. M. G. v. d. Werf (2014). <i>Life Cycle Assessment of French livestock products: Results of the AGRIBALYSE® program</i> . Proceedings of the 9th International Conference on Life Cycle Assessment in the Agri-Food Sector. San Francisco: 1154-1162.	2014	Conference	21.05	mediunAGRIBALYSE®
Lesschen, J. P., M. van den Berg, H. J. Westhoek, H. P. Witzke and O. Oenema (2011). "Greenhouse gas emission profiles of European livestock sectors." <i>Animal Feed Science and Technology</i> 166-167(0): 16-28.	2011	Journal	23.80	MITERRA-Europe model
Salou T., Espagnol S., Gac A., Ponchant P., Tocqueville A. I., Colomb V. and H. M. G. v. d. Werf (2014). <i>Life Cycle Assessment of French livestock products: Results of the AGRIBALYSE® program</i> . Proceedings of the 9th International Conference on Life Cycle Assessment in the Agri-Food Sector. San Francisco: 1154-1162.	2014	Conference	24.04	biophysical, mean AGRIBALYSE®
Salou T., Espagnol S., Gac A., Ponchant P., Tocqueville A. I., Colomb V. and H. M. G. v. d. Werf (2014). <i>Life Cycle Assessment of French livestock products: Results of the AGRIBALYSE® program</i> . Proceedings of the 9th International Conference on Life Cycle Assessment in the Agri-Food Sector. San Francisco: 1154-1162.	2014	Conference	24.25	biophysical, mean AGRIBALYSE®
Dollé J. B., A. Gac, V. Manneville, S. Moreau and E. Lorinquer (2012). Life cycle assessment on dairy and beef cattle farms in France. 8 th International Conference on Life Cycle Assessment in the Agri-Food Sector (LCA Food 2012). Saint Malo, France. Rennes.	2012	Conference	27.41	calf to beef steers 30 months old
Dollé J. B., A. Gac, V. Manneville, S. Moreau and E. Lorinquer (2012). Life cycle assessment on dairy and beef cattle farms in France. 8 th International Conference on Life Cycle Assessment in the Agri-Food Sector (LCA Food 2012). Saint Malo, France. Rennes.	2012	Conference	28.01	calf to beef young bulls 17 months old
Veysset, P., M. Lherm and D. Bébin (2010). "Energy consumption, greenhouse gas emissions and economic performance assessments in French Charolais suckler cattle farms: Model-based analysis and forecasts." <i>Agricultural Systems</i> 103(1): 41-50.	2010	Journal	29.50	
Dollé, J. B., A. Gac, V. Manneville, S. Moreau and E. Lorinquer (2012). Life cycle assessment on dairy and beef cattle farms in France. 8th International Conference on Life Cycle Assessment in the Agri-Food Sector (LCA Food 2012). Saint Malo, France. Rennes.	2012	Conference	30.44	calf to weanling 9-10 months old

Veysset, P., M. Lherm and D. Bébin (2010). "Energy consumption, greenhouse gas emissions and economic performance assessments in French Charolais suckler cattle farms: Model-based analysis and forecasts." <i>Agricultural Systems</i> 103(1): 41-50.	2010	Journal	37.76	conventional
Nguyen, T. T. H., H. M. G. van der Werf, Eugène M., Veysset P., Devun J., Chesneau G., Doreau M. (2012). <i>Effects of type of ration and allocation methods on the environmental impacts of beef-production systems</i> . <i>Livestock Science</i> 145(1-3): 239-251.	2010	Journal	38.85	Ext suckler, fibre, O3f
Nguyen, T. T. H., H. M. G. van der Werf, Eugène M., Veysset P., Devun J., Chesneau G., Doreau M. (2012). <i>Effects of type of ration and allocation methods on the environmental impacts of beef-production systems</i> . <i>Livestock Science</i> 145(1-3): 239-251.	2010	Journal	39.28	O3f Ext suckler, fibre
Nguyen, T. T. H., H. M. G. van der Werf, Eugène M., Veysset P., Devun J., Chesneau G., Doreau M. (2012). <i>Effects of type of ration and allocation methods on the environmental impacts of beef-production systems</i> . <i>Livestock Science</i> 145(1-3): 239-251.	2010	Journal	39.86	Ext suckler, maize,
Nguyen, T. T. H., H. M. G. van der Werf, Eugène M., Veysset P., Devun J., Chesneau G., Doreau M. (2012). <i>Effects of type of ration and allocation methods on the environmental impacts of beef-production systems</i> . <i>Livestock Science</i> 145(1-3): 239-251.	2010	Journal	40.00	Ext suckler, maize

Reference	Classification	System Boundaries	Functional Unit (FU)	GhG Emissions (kg CO2e / FU)	Allocation
Nguyen, T. T. H., H. M. G. van der Werf, Eugène M., Veysset P., Devun J., Chesneau G., Doreau M. (2012). <i>Effects of type of ration and allocation methods on the environmental impacts of beef-production systems</i> . <i>Livestock Science</i> 145(1-3): 239-251.	Case study	cradle to farm gate	kg carcass (farm gate); kg LWG (live weight gain)	27.0 - 27.9	live weight; protein; economic

Reference	Method/Boundaries/ Allocation	Management/Spacial scale	Footprint kg CO2e per kg LW	Notes
Veysset, P.; Lherm, M.; Bébin, D. Energy consumption, greenhouse gas emissions and economic performance assessments in French Charolais suckler cattle farms: Model-based analysis and forecasts. <i>Agri. Syst.</i> 2010, 103, 41-50.	IPCC Tier 2/cradle to farm gate/not specified	Conventional/study	14.3-18.3	Range in emissions for 5 beef production systems. May be suitable as a regional average, however allocation of dairy emissions is not specified.

Italy

Clune et al., 2017							
Reference	Year of study	Report type	kg CO ₂ -eq/kg produce, BFM after conversion	Notes (conventional farming assumed unless stated):			
Benatti L., Biolatti B., Cinotti S., Federici C., Montanari C., De Roest Kees, D. Rama, Brina N., Daga S., Mazzini V., Zuchi M., Marino M. and Pignatelli S. (2013). <i>The sustainability of beef to coop market</i> . Italy, coop.	2013	EPD	15.30	3. - a calf white meat for coop in italy white meat produced by italian breeders respecting the values of coop			
Benatti L., Biolatti B., Cinotti S., Federici C., Montanari C., De Roest Kees, D. Rama, Brina N., Daga S., Mazzini V., Zuchi M., Marino M. and Pignatelli S. (2013). <i>The sustainability of beef to coop market</i> . Italy, coop.	2013	EPD	18.20	1. adult beef (beef and scottona) for coop in italy meat of adult cattle breeders produced by italian respecting the values of coop			
Benatti L., Biolatti B., Cinotti S., Federici C., Montanari C., De Roest Kees, D. Rama, Brina N., Daga S., Mazzini V., Zuchi M., Marino M. and Pignatelli S. (2013). <i>The sustainability of beef to coop market</i> . Italy, coop.	2013	EPD	23.10				
Benatti L., Biolatti B., Cinotti S., Federici C., Montanari C., De Roest Kees, D. Rama, Brina N., Daga S., Mazzini V., Zuchi M., Marino M. and Pignatelli S. (2013). <i>The sustainability of beef to coop market</i> . Italy, coop.	2013	EPD	24.70	5 - adult cattle grazing in ireland - industry standard meat of adult bovine irish produced by kepák			
Lesschen, J. P., M. van den Berg, H. J. Westhoek, H. P. Witzke and O. Oenema (2011). "Greenhouse gas emission profiles of European livestock sectors." <i>Animal Feed Science and Technology</i> 166–167(0): 16-28.	2011	Journal	27.30	MITERRA-Europe model			
Summary of the study on the carbon footprint of New Zealand sheep meat and beef, 2022, Meat Industry Association, New Zealand. https://beeflambnz.com/knowledge-hub/PDF/summary-study-carbon-footprint-new-zealand-sheepmeat-and-beef.pdf							
Reference	Boundary	Farm type	Farm	Pro-cessing	Post-pro-cessing	Total Footprint	
			CO ₂ eq/kg meat				
Vitali A, Grossi G, Martino G, Bernabucci U, Nardone A, Lacetera L, 2018, Carbon footprint of organic beef meat from farm to fork: a case study of short supply chain. <i>Jurnal of the Science Food and Agriculture</i> , https://doi.org/10.1002/jsfa.9098	up to food consumption	organic beef	20.98	1.27	2.22	24.47	

United States of America

Clune et al., 2017					
Region	Reference	Year of study	Report type	kg CO ₂ -eq/kg produce, BFM after conversion	Notes (conventional farming assumed unless stated):
Nth America	Gerber, P. J., H. Steinfeld, B. Henderson, A. Mottet, C. Opio, J. Dijkman, A. Falcucci and G. Tempio (2013). Tackling climate change through livestock, A global assessment of emissions and mitigation opportunities. Rome, Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO).	2013	Report	41.73	
USA	Stackhouse-Lawson, K. R., C. A. Rotz, J. W. Oltjen and F. M. Mitloehner (2012). "Carbon footprint and ammonia emissions of California beef production systems." Journal of Animal Science 90(12): 4641-4655.	2012	Journal	22.30	A partial life cycle assessment (LCA) was conducted using the Integrated Farm System Model (IFSM)
USA	Benatti, L., B. Biolatti, S. Cinotti, C. Federici, C. Montanari, Kees, d. Roest, D. Rama, N. Brina, S. Daga, V. Mazzini, M. Zuchi, M. Marino and S. Pignatelli (2013). The sustainability of beef to coop market. Italy, coop.	2013	EPD	23.10	pasture
USA	Dunkley, C. S. and K. D. Dunkley (2013). "REVIEW - Greenhouse Gas Emissions from Livestock and Poultry, Agric Food Anal Bacteriol, 2013." Agric. Food Anal. Bacteriol 3:17-29.	2013	Journal	23.41	
USA	Stackhouse-Lawson, K. R., C. A. Rotz, J. W. Oltjen and F. M. Mitloehner (2012). "Carbon footprint and ammonia emissions of California beef production systems." Journal of Animal Science 90(12): 4641-4655.	2012	Journal	25.61	partial life cycle assessment (LCA) conducted using the Integrated Farm System Model (IFSM)
USA Mid-West	Johnson, D., H. Phetteplace, A. Seidl, U. Schneider and B. McCarl (2003). Management Variations for U.S. Beef Production Systems: Effects on Greenhouse Gas Emissions and China. 3rd International Methane and Nitrous Oxide Mitigation Conference, Beijing, China, China Coal Information Institute.	2003	Report	26.82	feedlot
USA Mid-West	Pelletier, N., R. Pirog and R. Rasmussen (2010). "Comparative life cycle environmental impacts of three beef production strategies in the Upper Midwestern United States." Agricultural Systems 103(6): 380-389.	2010	Journal	39.61	pasture finished
USA Mid-West	Pelletier, N., R. Pirog and R. Rasmussen (2010). "Comparative life cycle environmental impacts of three beef production strategies in the Upper Midwestern United States." Agricultural Systems 103(6): 380-389.	2010	Journal	30.53	feedlot finished

Reference	Classification	System Boundaries	Functional Unit (FU)	GhG Emissions (kg CO ₂ eq/ FU)	Allocation
Battagliese T., Andrade J., Schulze I., Uhlman B. & Barcan C. (2013). <i>More Sustainable Beef Optimization Project</i> . Phase 1 Final Report. BASF.	National sector	cradle to grave	1 lb consumed, boneless beef	23.6 (kg/lb)	
Capper J.L., Cady R.A. & Bauman D.E. (2009). <i>The environmental impact of dairy production: 1944 compared with 2007</i> . Journal of Animal Science. 87: 2160–7. doi:10.2527/jas.2009-1781	Comparison	cradle to grave	kg LW	Conv: 15.2 Grass finished: 26 Natural: 18	mass and economic
Capper J.L. (2011). <i>The environmental impact of beef production in the United States: 1977 compared with 2007</i> . Journal of Animal Science, 89: 4249–61. doi:10.2527/jas.2010-3784	Comparison	cradle to grave	kg of HCW beef	17.95	biological causality (dairy to beef)
Dudley Q.M., Liska A.J., Watson A.K. & Erickson G.E. (2014). <i>Uncertainties in life cycle greenhouse gas emissions from U.S. beef cattle</i> . Journal of Cleaner Production, 75: 31–39. doi:10.1016/j.jclepro.2014.03.087	Regional assessment	cradle to farm gate (cow-calf background feedlot)	kg LW	8 - 8.3	mass

FAO, 2016, *Environmental performance of large ruminant supply chains: Guidelines for assessment – Region Upper Midwest United States*

Reference	Classification	System Boundaries	Functional Unit (FU)	GhG Emissions (kg CO ₂ e / FU)	Allocation	Soil Carbon/ Sequestration	LuC / iLuC	Land use/ occupation
Pelletier N., Pirog R. & Rasmussen R. (2010). <i>Comparative life cycle environmental impacts of three beef production strategies in the Upper Midwestern United States</i> . Agricultural Systems, 103: 380–389. doi:10.1016/j.agsy.2010.03.009	Comparison	cradle to farm gate	kg LW	Feed lot finished: 19.2, Pasture finished: 14.8	No cow/calf allocation. Biophysical properties (rations)	constant assumed	not mentioned	ecological footprint was used instead of land occupation

Summary of the study on the carbon footprint of New Zealand sheepmeat and beef, 2022, Meat Industry Association, New Zealand.

<https://beeflambnz.com/knowledge-hub/PDF/summary-study-carbon-footprint-new-zealand-sheepmeat-and-beef.pdf>

Reference	Boundary	Farm type	Farm	Processing	Post processing	Total Footprint
			CO ₂ eq/kg meat			
Sanders, K. T., & Webber, M. E. (2014). A comparative analysis of the greenhouse gas emissions intensity of wheat and beef in the United States. Environmental Research Letters, 9(4), 044011. https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1748-9326/9/4/044011/pdf	up to food consumption	/	27	0.39	3.43	30.82
Asem-Hiablíe S, Battagliese T, Stackhouse-Lawson KR, Alan Rotz C (2019). A life cycle assessment of the environmental impacts of a beef system in the USA. <i>International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment</i> , 24(3), 441-455. https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-018-1464-6 *data was adjusted to a meat equating to 40% of Live Weight	grave	pasture + feedlot	30.67*	0.59*	3.84*	35.10*

Latin America and Caribbean

Clune at al., 2017				
Reference	Year of study	Report type	kg CO ₂ -eq/kg produce, BFM after conversion	Notes (conventional farming assumed unless stated):
Gerber, P. J., H. Steinfeld, B. Henderson, A. Mottet, C. Opio, J. Dijkman, A. Falcucci and G. Tempio (2013). <i>Tackling climate change through livestock, A global assessment of emissions and mitigation opportunities</i> . Rome, Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO).	2013	Report	69.06	-
Gerber, P. J., H. Steinfeld, B. Henderson, A. Mottet, C. Opio, J. Dijkman, A. Falcucci and G. Tempio (2013). <i>Tackling climate change through livestock, A global assessment of emissions and mitigation opportunities</i> . Rome, Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO).	2013	Report	48.92	-

Argentina

Clune at al., 2017				
Reference	Year of study	Report type	kg CO ₂ -eq/kg produce, BFM after conversion	Notes (conventional farming assumed unless stated):
González A. D., Frostell B. and Carlsson-Kanyama A. (2011). "Protein efficiency per unit energy and per unit greenhouse gas emissions: Potential contribution of diet choices to climate change mitigation." <i>Food Policy</i> 36(5): 562-570.	2011	Journal	22.00	
Benatti L., Biolatti B., Cinotti S., Federici C., Montanari C., De Roest Kees, D. Rama, Brina N., Daga S., Mazzini V., Zuchi M., Marino M. and Pignatelli S. (2013). <i>The sustainability of beef to coop market</i> . Italy, coop.	2013	EPD	28.80	
Benatti L., Biolatti B., Cinotti S., Federici C., Montanari C., De Roest Kees, D. Rama, Brina N., Daga S., Mazzini V., Zuchi M., Marino M. and Pignatelli S. (2013). <i>The sustainability of beef to coop market</i> . Italy, coop.	2015	EPD	35.00	feedlot

Brazil

Clune at al., 2017				
Reference	Year of study	Report type	kg CO ₂ -eq/kg produce, BFM after conversion	Notes (conventional farming assumed unless stated):
Schroeder R., L. K. Aguiar and R. Baines (2012). <i>Carbon Footprint in Meat Production and Supply Chains</i> . <i>Journal of Food Science and Engineering</i> 2: 652-665.	2012	Journal	25.40	
Benatti L., Biolatti B., Cinotti S., Federici C., Montanari C., De Roest Kees, D. Rama, Brina N., Daga S., Mazzini V., Zuchi M., Marino M. and Pignatelli S. (2013). <i>The sustainability of beef to coop market</i> . Italy, coop.	2014	EPD	29.00	feedlot

Kamali F. P., M. P. M. Meuwissen and A. G. J. M. O. Lansink (2014). Evaluation of beef sustainability in conventional, organic, and mixed crop-beef supply chains. Proceedings of the 9th International Conference on Life Cycle Assessment in the Agri-Food Sector. San Francisco: 619-627.	2014	Conference	30.03	mixed
Cederberg, C., U. M. Persson, K. Neovius, S. Molander and R. Clift (2011). <i>Including Carbon Emissions from Deforestation in the Carbon Footprint of Brazilian Beef</i> Environmental Science & Technology 45(5): 1773-1779.	2011	Journal	30.23	
Kamali, F. P., M. P. M. Meuwissen and A. G. J. M. O. Lansink (2014). Evaluation of beef sustainability in conventional, organic, and mixed crop-beef supply chains. Proceedings of the 9th International Conference on Life Cycle Assessment in the Agri-Food Sector. San Francisco: 619-627.	2014	Conference	33.12	organic
Kamali, F. P., M. P. M. Meuwissen and A. G. J. M. O. Lansink (2014). Evaluation of beef sustainability in conventional, organic, and mixed crop-beef supply chains. Proceedings of the 9th International Conference on Life Cycle Assessment in the Agri-Food Sector. San Francisco: 619-627.	2014	Conference	33.74	conventional
Benatti, L., B. Biolatti, S. Cinotti, C. Federici, C. Montanari, Kees, d. Roest, D. Rama, N. Brina, S. Daga, V. Mazzini, M. Zuchi, M. Marino and S. Pignatelli (2013). The sustainability of beef to coop market. Italy, coop.	2013	EPD	34.10	feedlot
Cederberg, C., Meyer, D. & Flysjö, A., (2009), Life Cycle Inventory of greenhouse gas emissions and use of land and energy of Brazilian beef exported to Europe, SIK-Rapport 792, accessed 13/02/2015 from http://www.konkurrensverket.se/globalassets/upphandling/hallbarhet/life-cycle-inventory-of-greenhouse-gas-emissions-and-use-of-land-and-energy-in-brazilian-beef-production-sik-2009792.pdf	2009	Report	40.29	
Hallström E., Rööös E., Börjesson P. (2014). <i>Sustainable meat consumption: A quantitative analysis of nutritional intake, greenhouse gas emissions and land use from a Swedish perspective</i> . Food Policy 47(0): 81-90.	2014	Journal	41.00	
Schroeder, R., L. K. Aguiar and R. Baines (2012). <i>Carbon Footprint in Meat Production and Supply Chains</i> . Journal of Food Science and Engineering 2: 652-665.	2012	Journal	45.17	
Cederberg, C., U. M. Persson, K. Neovius, S. Molander and R. Clift (2011). <i>Including Carbon Emissions from Deforestation in the Carbon Footprint of Brazilian Beef</i> . Environmental Science & Technology 45(5): 1773-1779.	2011	Journal	46.95	
Blonk, H., A. Kool, B. Luske and S. d. Waart (2008). Environmental effects of protein-rich food products in the Netherlands Consequences of animal protein substitutes Gouda, Blonk Milieuadvies.	2008	Report	58.33	
Mieleitner, J., M. Alig, F. Grandl, T. Nemecek and G. r. Gaillard (2012). Environmental impact of beef – role of slaughtering, meat processing and transport. 8th International Conference on Life Cycle Assessment in the Agri-Food Sector (LCA Food 2012). Saint Malo, France. Rennes.	2012	Conference	64.00	

Reference	Classification	System Boundaries	Functional Unit (FU)	GhG Emissions (kg CO2e / FU)	Allocation
Dick, M., Abreu da Silva, M. & Dewes, H. 2014. <i>Life cycle assessment of beef cattle production in two typical grassland systems of southern Brazil</i> . Journal of Cleaner Production 1–9. doi:10.1016/j.jclepro.2014.01.080	Case study	cradle to farm gate	kg LW	22.5 (extensive); 9.2 (improved)	not needed - single product (LWG)

Reference	Method/Boundaries/ Allocation	Management /Spacial scale	Footprint kg CO ₂ eq per kg LW	Notes
Cederberg, C.; Persson, U.M.; Neovius, K.; Molander, S.; Clift, R. <i>Including carbon emissions from deforestation in the carbon footprint of Brazilian beef</i> . Environ. Sci. Tech. 2011, 45, 1773–1779.	IPCC Tier 1 + literature survey/ cradle to farm gate / primary product based	Conventional/national	14.3	Spatial attribution of emissions from LUC has a significant impact on emissions and range from 22 to 370 kg CO ₂ eq. per kg LW. Value given is at the national scale, amortized over 20 years. Values have been converted from kg CO ₂ eq. per kg carcass weight.
		Conventional/national	22.4	

Sudaharian Africa

Clune et al., 2017					
Reference	Year of study	Report type	kg CO ₂ -eq/kg produce, BFM after conversion	Notes (conventional farming assumed unless stated):	
Gerber, P. J., H. Steinfeld, B. Henderson, A. Mottet, C. Opio, J. Dijkman, A. Falcucci and G. Tempio (2013). <i>Tackling climate change through livestock, A global assessment of emissions and mitigation opportunities</i> . Rome, Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO).	2013	Report	100.72		

North Africa

Clune et al., 2017					
Reference	Year of study	Report type	kg CO ₂ -eq/kg produce, BFM after conversion	Notes (conventional farming assumed unless stated):	
Gerber P. J., H. Steinfeld, B. Henderson, A. Mottet, C. Opio, J. Dijkman, A. Falcucci and G. Tempio (2013). <i>Tackling climate change through livestock, A global assessment of emissions and mitigation opportunities</i> . Rome, Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO).	2013	Report	40.29	-	